

Paris Conference

on Risks from Mirror Life

Meeting Report | June 12-13, 2025

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Pasteur

*Mirror Biology
Dialogues Fund*

Paris Conference on Risks from Mirror Life: Meeting Report

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This report summarizes presentations and discussions from the Paris Conference on Risks from Mirror Life held at Institut Pasteur, Paris, on June 12-13, 2025. The views and opinions expressed by speakers and participants are their own and do not necessarily reflect the official positions of Institut Pasteur, Mirror Biology Dialogues Fund, or their affiliated institutions. The report endeavours to represent the discussions at the conference and the preceding virtual roundtables, but errors are possible. To report an error in this report, please contact info@parismirrorlife.org.

The Institut Pasteur is a private, non-profit international research and education foundation that is committed to advancing science, medicine and public health. The Mirror Biology Dialogues Fund (MBDF) is a U.S. 501(c)(3) non-profit that works to advance the global discussion to chart the path forward for mirror biology research. MBDF is supported by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, the David and Lucile Packard Foundation, the Dreamery Foundation, the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation, Open Philanthropy, and Patrick Collison.

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Foreword

Prof. Yasmine Belkaid, President, Institut Pasteur

Scientists play many roles in society—as creators of knowledge, problem solvers and innovators, educators, advisors, participants in democracy, global citizens, and ethical stewards. The potential creation of mirror life demands engagement from the global scientific community in all of these capacities.

The risks from mirror life warrant serious consideration. The dangers to humans, animals, plants, and ecosystems appear extraordinary, perhaps unprecedented. As scientists, we must always remain open to evidence that could change our understanding. However, given the stakes and what we already know, it is difficult to imagine obtaining contrary evidence strong enough to justify the creation of mirror life. It seems clear that mirror life should not be created.

We have a rare and remarkable opportunity to address the risks of mirror life in advance of their realization. I would like to offer my appreciation, in particular, to those scientists who previously held the goal of creating mirror life and have ultimately abandoned their efforts and argued for mirror life to not be created. They are role models of responsible science. Scientists have a responsibility to bring our best understanding of these risks to global attention, and society has a responsibility to deliberate and act while there is time to do so.

I was honored to host the conference described in this report at the Institut Pasteur. The Institut was an appropriate location in many ways, and not only because its namesake Louis Pasteur originally discovered the property of molecular chirality that fundamentally underlies the nature of mirror life. The Institut Pasteur is also committed to considering the ethics of innovation and bringing together stakeholders from around the world for discussions about science, technology, and society. Through its involvement in the Pasteur Network, an international network of more than 30 institutions in 25 countries, our institute is uniquely positioned to address global scientific challenges.

As you will read in this report, there was considerable debate about how to prioritize additional research on the risks of mirror life and related biological systems, and how best to take long-term action to mitigate those risks. But there was also substantial agreement that, based on our current understanding, mirror life should not be created and that governance will be needed to prevent its creation. It is my hope that the outputs of the meeting in Paris will directly inform further research, additional discussions, and ultimately the creation of intelligent policies that can address risks without unnecessarily hampering science.

As we move forward to determine what should be done about the risks of mirror life, we need to keep in mind what is at stake. The risks being discussed are uniquely serious, and I hope that we will act with foresight to prevent them from occurring, setting an example for future efforts to bring forward emerging risks for prudent deliberation and collective action.

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A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Y. Belkaid', written in a cursive style.

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Participants

The Paris Conference on Risks from Mirror Life involved:

335 participants from **31** different countries

142 in-person and **193** virtual attendees for the Symposium on Day 1

86 attendees for the Workshop on Day 2

38 pre-conference virtual roundtable participants

Pre-conference virtual roundtable participants

The Paris Conference on Mirror Life workshops were preceded by a series of virtual roundtable discussions to shape the meeting agenda and facilitate contributions from individuals who were unable to attend the in-person meeting. Participants in the virtual roundtable discussions included those listed below. A participant's name being listed here does not imply endorsement of the content of this report.

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Conference speakers presented at the Symposium on day 1 of the Paris Conference on Risks from Mirror Life. A speaker's name being listed here does not imply endorsement of the content of this report.

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John Glass, J. Craig Venter Institute

Filippa Lentzos, King's College London

David Relman, Stanford University

Workshop participants

Participants in the in-person workshops at the Paris Conference on Risks From Mirror Life included those listed below. A participant's name being listed here does not imply endorsement of the content of this report.

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Introduction

For decades, biologists have speculated about the possibility of creating “mirror life”: organisms in which all biomolecules are the mirror images of their naturally-occurring forms (also referred to as having reversed chirality). All natural-chirality organisms use “right-handed” nucleic acids and “left-handed” proteins, while mirror organisms would use the opposite configuration. Some researchers have taken early steps toward mirror life; for instance, in 2019 the U.S. National Science Foundation awarded a \$4M grant for “Booting up a Mirror Cell”.^{1,2} Some potential risks of mirror life had been acknowledged,^{3,4} but they had not yet been thoroughly examined and were not widely understood.

Against this backdrop, an article in *Science* titled “Confronting Risks of Mirror Life” was published in December 2024 by an international and interdisciplinary working group of 38 leading researchers, including two Nobel Laureates and 16 members of national academies.⁵ Several authors had previously pursued the creation of mirror life themselves before stopping because of its risks. The article summarized the findings of a comprehensive 300-page technical report assessing the feasibility and risks of creating mirror organisms.⁶ It concluded that mirror organisms could be created in the next 10-30 years, that they could pose unprecedented risks to humans, animals, plants, and ecosystems, and that a global conversation was needed about how to proceed responsibly.

In the months following the release of the article and technical report, the topic of mirror life has attracted substantial and constructive engagement from the scientific community and beyond. Major international news outlets have covered the topic of mirror life, drawing increased public attention.⁷⁻¹⁰ And at a February global summit marking the 50th anniversary of the 1975 Asilomar Conference on Recombinant DNA, there was broad agreement that the risks of mirror life far outweigh its benefits,¹¹ and a statement asserting that “mirror life should not be created” was signed by nearly 100 participants from over 20 countries.¹²

To continue the conversation, on June 12-13 2025 the Institut Pasteur hosted the Paris Conference on Risks from Mirror Life. The event was co-hosted by the Mirror Biology Dialogues Fund, a philanthropically-funded nonprofit established in collaboration with authors of the December 2024 *Science* article and dedicated to understanding and addressing risks from mirror life. This report summarizes the discussions at the conference. The first day brought together more than 300 scientists, ethicists, civil society group representatives, and policymakers in-person and virtually from more than 30 countries; the second day was dedicated to workshop discussions with 86 attendees. The conference was also preceded by several virtual roundtable discussions with attendees and key stakeholders who were unable to attend; these roundtables informed the structure and content of the workshops on the second day of the conference, and key takeaways are integrated into the workshop summaries.

Executive Summary and Recommendations

Symposium: June 12, 2025

On the first day of the conference, a public Symposium presented perspectives on the current scientific understanding of mirror life and its potential risks, as well as discussion of how scientists can work with society to understand and address those risks. All presentations were recorded on video and are available online.¹³ The presentations drew heavily from analyses described in the 2024 *Science* article “Confronting Risks of Mirror Life”⁵ and its accompanying technical report.⁶ The presenters’ key points were as follows:

- After a brief introduction from **Prof. David Bikard (Institut Pasteur)**, **Prof. Filippa Lentzos (King’s College London)** summarized some of the recent history of the governance of risks of biotechnology. Noting the challenges of governing these risks given the acceleration of biotechnology research and the expansion of access to its tools, she argued that proactive discussion on the risks of mirror life served as a commendable example of responsible science.
- **Prof. John Glass (J. Craig Venter Institute)** argued that mirror organisms could most plausibly be created through the bottom-up assembly of components including a mirror-image DNA genome, cytoplasm (including mirror-image ribosomes), and membranes, though other pathways might be possible. Progress had been made in these areas prior to the 2024 article, and while no researchers are known to be pursuing the creation of mirror life, work is ongoing on some of its precursor technologies. If a mirror bacterium were created, perfect containment would likely be impossible because of imperfect biosafety and the ongoing risk of deliberate release.
- **Prof. Deepa Agashe (National Centre for Biological Sciences, Bangalore)** explained that if a mirror bacterium was released into the environment, it could grow on achiral and some chiral nutrients (albeit at a reduced rate), and its reversed chirality would plausibly make it difficult or impossible for bacterial predators to detect, attack, or digest them. If growth rates exceed death rates, as seems likely, the result would be sustained population expansion and invasion of ecological niches worldwide, with the potential to cause mass extinctions, large-scale ecosystem disruptions, and persistent risk of infections for multicellular life. It is difficult to foresee countermeasures that would prevent more than a small fraction of the harm from such a threat.
- **Prof. David Relman (Stanford University)** argued that mirror bacteria could enter multicellular lifeforms (including humans, animals, and potentially plants) passively through ingestion, inhalation, and/or routine surface abrasions. Once inside of a host, they could find sufficient achiral and chiral nutrients to grow, and their reversed chirality may render major components of the immune system ineffective. Absent an effective immune defense, mirror bacteria would multiply, leading to cellular, tissue, and organ dysfunction and death of the host. It is likely possible to design medical countermeasures for humans, but they would be profoundly difficult to deliver to the world’s population and they could not be scalably adapted to protect the world’s plants, animals, and biosphere.

Workshop: June 13, 2025

On the second day of the conference, expert-led workshops explored key unresolved questions across five parallel tracks. The structure and content of the workshop tracks were informed by virtual roundtable discussions prior to the conference.

- In the *Risk & Benefit Assessment of Mirror Life* track, participants discussed the current body of evidence for the risks and benefits of mirror organisms. Nearly the entire group agreed that based on available evidence, the risks of building mirror organisms far outweigh the plausible benefits, which can be largely achieved with alternative means, and that the international governance community should move forward with efforts to robustly prevent the creation of mirror organisms. While there was some disagreement about the strength of current immunological and ecological evidence, the group was unable to identify one or a small number of key experiments that they thought might significantly change the risk assessment in the near term, though they agreed that research would be valuable for determining the scale of risk and informing future preparedness, detection, and response efforts. Some noted that further research might change their conclusions about the risks of mirror life, but many argued that such research should not block efforts to establish governance.
- In the *Technical Feasibility and Development Pathways* track, participants identified four key technical milestones toward mirror life as potential opportunities for governance: a fully synthetic natural-chirality or mirror-image ribosome; a fully-defined, successfully “booted” synthetic natural-chirality cell; an *in vitro* mirror-image genome; and a natural-chirality “Protein synthesis Using Recombinant Elements” (PURE) system efficient enough to be self-sustaining. Participants generally considered that the first two milestones would be more difficult to achieve than the latter two, implying that the former might be effective points for potential regulatory controls. A fully synthetic natural-chirality or mirror-image ribosome was considered by some as the most difficult step on the pathway to mirror life and therefore as a potential area for regulation; however, there was disagreement about whether scientific interest or applications of such ribosomes would justify their pursuit. The booting of synthetic cells from fully-defined components was considered to be a less immediate scientific priority compared to synthetic cell booting experiments that use cell-derived mixtures such as cell lysate, and was identified as another promising stopping point for research.
- In the *Preparedness and Countermeasures* track, the group agreed that there are no currently identifiable physical or biological containment strategies that could fully secure mirror organisms against deliberate release, and no currently foreseeable countermeasures that could plausibly mitigate the bulk of the risks of mirror organisms in the event of their release; that any countermeasures research does not require and must not develop technologies that would facilitate the creation of mirror organisms; and that if countries pursue countermeasures development, they should do so in a collaborative and transparent fashion to avoid triggering geopolitical security issues. The effectiveness and risks of some speculative potential countermeasures remained open questions.
- In the *Principles for the Path Forward* track, participants discussed general principles to guide future efforts to address risks from mirror life. They agreed that based on current understanding, the creation of mirror life should be “indefinitely prohibited,” that governance of its precursor

technologies would be necessary to ensure this outcome, and that a broad and international set of stakeholders should be involved in developing governance, including governments, civil society groups, international fora, scientists, ethicists, and industry. They acknowledged that in theory, new evidence could change their recommendations and noted the importance of preserving the benefits of life science research and avoiding overregulation of synthetic biology.

- In the *Policy Interface* track, participants agreed that despite some remaining scientific uncertainties, there is sufficient evidence of the substantial risks and minimal potential benefits of mirror organisms to begin considering governance measures to ensure that they are not created, including norms, soft law, and hard law. Several participants argued that, as currently understood, the risks of mirror organisms were so large that a more precise risk-benefit analysis would be unlikely to change the result, and one noted that waiting for more evidence imposes some additional risk that effective governance will become impossible as progress is made towards overcoming technical obstacles to mirror life. Many agreed that a sensible short-term policy goal would be for public and private funders to make clear that they will not fund research with the goal of creating mirror organisms. The group was more uncertain about specific longer-term policy goals, in part because of a lack of technical knowledge about the tradeoffs involved with regulating various precursor technologies for mirror life. They recommended global engagement with a wide variety of stakeholders, including but not limited to technical experts, to develop potential regulations.

Recommendations

Based on the discussions summarized in this report, the following recommendations are offered by the Steering Committee to guide further efforts to manage the risks of mirror organisms:

1. Researchers should refrain from pursuing the creation of mirror organisms, and both public and private funders should make clear that they will not support research aimed at this goal.
2. Work should start now to develop frameworks for governing key technical milestones on the pathways to mirror life, with consideration of hard and soft law at institutional, national, and international levels. Input should be sought from governments, scientists, funding bodies, standard-setting institutions, international organizations, communicators, social scientists, civil society networks and publics, ethicists, and industry groups.
3. Efforts to mitigate the risks of mirror organisms should preserve scientific freedom and the potential benefits of life-science research to the maximum extent possible.
4. Further research should be conducted into the risks and potential benefits of mirror organisms, for determining the scale of risk and informing future preparedness, detection, and response efforts, as long as this research does not itself advance the creation of mirror organisms and is performed in an open and transparent fashion.

Summary of Day 1: Symposium Lectures

Opening Remarks

David Bikard, PhD, Synthetic Biology Lab, Institut Pasteur

Prof. David Bikard opened the Symposium by welcoming participants and highlighting the significance of discussing mirror life at the Institut Pasteur. He recalled Louis Pasteur's foundational discovery of chirality in biology, an observation that 170 years later now underpins the Symposium's discussion of the risks of mirror life. He reminded participants that they are also here today thanks to the work done by the researchers who together wrote the *Science* article⁵ and accompanying technical report⁶ that first outlined the risks of mirror life in detail. Prof. Bikard described the two key goals for the Symposium as 1) to communicate current scientific understanding of mirror life feasibility, risks, and emerging governance conversations to a broad audience, and 2) to convene diverse stakeholders to determine next steps.

The International Conversation on Mirror Life

Filippa Lentzos, PhD, King's College London

Prof. Filippa Lentzos opened the first seminar by discussing the history of responsible governance in biotechnology. She began by highlighting the legacy of Louis Pasteur and recounting the 1975 "Berg Letter"¹⁴ and subsequent Asilomar Conference on Recombinant DNA that fifty years ago sought to "set standards allowing geneticists to push research to its limits without endangering public health."¹⁵ She noted that the Biological Weapons Convention (BWC) also entered into force in 1975, an example of the international community coming together to prohibit the

development, production, stockpiling, or use of biological weapons. She remarked that ongoing advancements in the life sciences, including synthetic biology, are now a significant driver of increased security concerns.

Today, she explained, we face a similar moment, but with arguably much higher stakes: biotechnology is accelerating and is becoming more accessible to a much broader set of actors, and sources of research funding and their associated agendas have diversified beyond traditional academic communities.

In February, Prof. Lentzos recounted, the Spirit of Asilomar and the Future of Biotechnology summit brought together some 300 scientists, bioethicists, and biosecurity experts to again discuss responsible bioscience. As in 1975, they asked: are there some experiments or technologies that are so risky they simply should not be pursued? Prof. Lentzos then herself asked: are we any closer to developing red lines around genetic engineering research, and should we be? She noted that at the 2025 Spirit of Asilomar summit, despite the complexity of answering these questions, general agreement did form around a particularly risky line of inquiry—mirror life. Summit participants broadly affirmed that creating mirror life presents a clear red line that should not be crossed.¹¹

Biotechnology is accelerating and is becoming more accessible to a much broader set of actors.

Prof. Lentzos went on to define mirror life as lifeforms composed of mirror-image biological molecules. While these organisms do not exist in nature and cannot arise from existing life, scientists have already created mirror-image nucleic acids

and proteins. Prof. Lentzos emphasized that these mirror-image biomolecules do not by themselves pose risks and have potential scientific and therapeutic applications. However, as enabling technologies continue to progress, there are several plausible pathways to create mirror organisms in the lab. Prof. Lentzos went on to explain the key concern: mirror life presents potentially unprecedented risks through evasion of ecological and immune defenses to humans, animals, plants, and the environment. Meanwhile, mirror life appears to offer few foreseeable benefits.

In December 2024, a group of 38 scientists—including Nobel laureates, members of national academics, and researchers from 10 countries—published a paper in *Science* and an accompanying 300-page technical report raising concerns about mirror life. Together, these documents laid out risks, projected timelines, and suggested a path forward. They estimated that mirror life could be created in 10 to 30 years and called for early action to address the risks.

Prof. Lentzos emphasized that the authors of the *Science* paper “welcomed arguments and evidence about mirror life that they had not yet considered” and called on the global community, including scientists, policymakers, and civil society, to consider these risks and potential governance mechanisms that could prevent the creation of mirror life without unnecessarily impeding scientific research. To that end, the Paris Symposium served as an opportunity for global discussion.

Prof. Lentzos reflected that, while she was not an author of the *Science* paper or technical report, she agreed that mirror organisms should not be created and endorsed the wider initiative. She noted that in the time since the Berg Letter was written in 1975, expectations for the ethical standards of life-science research have expanded to include the

responsible stewardship of science, security, biodiversity, ecosystems, and environments, as well as inclusiveness, collaboration, and social and intergenerational justice. Today’s standards also call for a commitment to exercise caution, mitigate harmful consequences, and develop policies based on shared values.¹⁶ Prof. Lentzos argued that the mirror life initiative has so far embodied all of these aspects of scientific stewardship and, in her mind, constitutes an exemplary role model of responsible science today.

Discussion highlights

Asked about her role in the development of the WHO’s Global Guidance Framework for the Responsible Use of the Life Sciences,¹⁶ Prof. Lentzos explained that the process included wide stakeholder consultations and expert working groups over 2–3 years. Reflecting on the implications for potential governance of mirror life, she emphasized that finding consensus across disciplines and geographic contexts is challenging but entirely feasible with long-term commitment and funding.

When asked why preventing mirror life should be prioritized when many other serious risks are already present, Prof. Lentzos responded that mirror life presents a rare opportunity for the scientific community to coalesce around preemptively addressing an exceptionally weighty problem.

In response to a question about the risks of overregulation, Prof. Lentzos clarified that any regulations should be carefully and narrowly targeted towards the creation of mirror life. She emphasized the importance of cultivating shared understanding of the risks so that regulations become part of scientific culture and not just bureaucratic red tape.

Pathways to Mirror Life

John Glass, PhD, J. Craig Venter Institute (JCVI)

Prof. John Glass opened his seminar by sharing his own experience as part of a 2019 U.S. National Science Foundation Ideas Workshop that brought together 80 synthetic biologists to conceive of novel ideas. One of these ideas was the creation of mirror life, which faced no objection at the time—an example of how siloed thinking can fail to consider risks that others might recognize. Today, alongside his co-authors of the 2024 *Science* paper, he believes that the risks of creating mirror life far outweigh any potential benefits. However, he clarified, his seminar would focus primarily on the feasibility of and potential pathways to creating mirror life.

Prof. Glass began by explaining that all major biomolecules are chiral: they can exist in two different mirror-image versions of their molecular structure. He highlighted the tragic example of thalidomide, a drug containing equal parts of the molecule's mirrored pairs, which was formerly marketed to pregnant women for morning

sickness. He noted that today it is well known that while “right-handed” thalidomide is a sedative, “left-handed” thalidomide causes birth defects.

Prof. Glass explained that a mirror bacterium would be constructed from mirror-image biomolecules, and that applications of mirror bacteria might include improved efficiency of biomanufacturing of certain mirror-image biomolecules for therapeutic purposes. In principle, mirror bacteria would function identically to natural-chirality life in isolation, but in the natural environment they could pose significant risks to humans, animals, plants, and ecosystems. He noted that subsequent seminar speakers would elaborate on how mirror bacteria may evade recognition, degradation, and digestion by predators and immune cells.

Prof. Glass then moved on to argue that mirror bacteria could be created in 10–30 years. He outlined two plausible pathways: a more likely “bottom-up” approach of chemically synthesizing mirror-image components, assembling them, and then booting up a functional mirror cell; and a less likely “top-down” approach of building a mirror-image biochemical system inside of a living

Figure 1: The “bottom-up” approach of chemically synthesizing a mirror bacterium would require 1) the synthesis of a mirror-image DNA genome, 2) mirror-image cytoplasm, including mirror-image ribosomes (the foundation for a cell-free transcription-translation or TXTL system), and 3) mirror-image membranes to then 4) assemble and “boot up” as a functional cell.

natural chirality cell and then removing the natural-chirality components.

Prof. Glass elaborated that the bottom-up approach would require 1) the synthesis of a mirror-image DNA genome, 2) mirror-image cytoplasm, including mirror-image ribosomes (the foundation for a cell-free transcription-translation or TXTL system), and 3) mirror-image membranes to then 4) assemble and “boot up” as a functional cell. He outlined several recent advances that make this more feasible, including: the *in vitro* production of a synthetic 580-kilobase natural mycoplasma genome;¹⁷ the creation of the first cell with an entirely chemically synthesized genome;¹⁸ the design and synthesis of a new, minimal genome used to build a cell;¹⁹ the chemical synthesis and assembly of kilobase-length mirror-image nucleic acids;²⁰ and the first reported *in vitro* biogenesis of a natural-chirality ribosome.²¹

Prof. Glass summarized by arguing that synthesizing a mirror-image genome today is possible, but would require significant investment; that there is a clear path to mirror-image translation systems but with significant technical barriers; that the molecules needed for a functional membrane can already be synthesized; and that he believes it will likely soon be feasible to “boot up” synthetic natural-chirality cells.

Moving from the feasibility of creating mirror bacteria to the challenges of containing it, Prof. Glass asserted that perfect biocontainment is not realistic because all methods are vulnerable to human error or deliberate misuse and mirror bacteria could present novel biosecurity and biosafety challenges. Physical containment has well-documented failure rates, biocontainment measures can be reversed with basic techniques, and even a single failure could lead to environmental proliferation. Prof. Glass concluded that scientific and political efforts to establish

governance measures should begin today to address potential risks before they are realized.

Prof. Glass asserted that perfect biocontainment is not realistic because all methods are vulnerable to human error or deliberate misuse and mirror bacteria could present novel biosecurity and biosafety challenges.

Discussion highlights

During the Q&A, Prof. Glass was asked about advances in creating synthetic natural cells enabling the creation of mirror cells. He argued that synthetic cells hold great potential as a useful future biotechnology and suggested instead aiming to never produce fully synthetic mirror-image genomes or possibly mirror-image ribosomes.

When asked how companies could use mirror biology research, he explained that synthesized mirror-image proteins or nucleic acids could be useful and do not pose the same risks as mirror life since they cannot self-replicate. He elaborated that mirror-image molecules with the same shape and functionality of existing drugs could be less immunogenic and resist degradation, so they could in theory last much longer.

On the question of biocontainment, Prof. Glass noted that the highest level of biosafety (BSL-4) for laboratories is still subject to risks of human error and malfeasance. He emphasized that once the first mirror organism is created, the danger of an accidental or deliberate release could persist indefinitely.

When asked about bottlenecks to the top-down pathway for developing mirror life, he explained that if existing ribosomes could be engineered to produce both L- and D-proteins, developers would still need to assign new molecular machinery for attaching each amino acid to its corresponding

transfer RNA (tRNA) and develop a way to contain natural and mirror-image nucleic acids together in the same cell without disrupting its function.

When asked if emerging technologies such as AI could accelerate timelines to the creation of mirror life, Prof. Glass said that it is possible, but not obvious. He pointed to how the latest version of the AI program AlphaFold can design proteins and posited that, for example, AI would not be helpful in designing a D-amino acid insulin, but that it could help to design a D-protein with the same function and enzymatic activity as insulin but with a different sequence and structure.

Mirror Bacteria and the Environment

Deepa Agashe, PhD, National Centre for Biological Sciences, Bengaluru

Prof. Agashe began her seminar by explaining how basic ecological principles can be applied to assess whether mirror bacteria could persist in natural environments. She explained that changes in the population of any organism fundamentally depend upon whether its birth rate (determined largely by food availability and competition) exceeds its death rate (influenced mainly by predation, infection, and abiotic stressors).

The birth rate of mirror bacteria would depend heavily upon its access to viable nutrients. Prof. Agashe explained that nutrient access would

depend on the “chassis” species used to build mirror bacteria, providing two extreme examples. First, a photoautotrophic mirror *Synechococcus* bacterium would only require sunlight and CO₂, so it could survive in nutrient-poor environments like the open ocean. Alternatively, a chemoheterotroph mirror *E. coli* would require organic compounds to survive. Since *E. coli* is often used in synthetic biology research, the creation of a mirror *E. coli* is the more likely scenario, so her analysis focused on this example.

Without additional engineering, mirror *E. coli* would only have limited ability to utilize most natural-chirality nutrients (e.g., most L-amino acids, many sugars like D-glucose), but it could grow on achiral organic compounds such as glycerol and uric acid that are widely available in soil and water, as well as some chiral nutrients. Prof. Agashe cited several studies showing that natural *E. coli* can grow solely (i.e., in a minimal medium supplemented with a single, specific nutrient) on many different achiral carbon and nitrogen sources.^{22–23} She then explained that environmental concentrations of these nutrients range from 1–1000 µg/L in water and 0.8–8 mg/L in soil. Since *E. coli* has been demonstrated to need only 100–1000 µg/L of these nutrients for growth, mirror *E. coli* or other similar mirror bacteria may have positive birth rates in most natural environments, though they would likely be lower than the birth rates of natural-chirality bacteria. Mirror bacteria could also plausibly be engineered

Figure 2: Mirror bacteria could colonize and spread through various ecosystems. Animals and plants may be continuously exposed with cyclical transmission between animals and humans, creating potentially severe effects on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems.

to consume some abundant natural-chirality nutrients like glucose, enabling them to proliferate more easily in natural environments.

The death rate of mirror bacteria would depend heavily on their vulnerability to predation. Prof. Agashe explained how their reversed chirality would make them immune to bacteriophages and could make it difficult or impossible for protists and other predators to track, recognize, internalize, kill, or digest them. She also noted that many mechanisms of bacterial “warfare” depend on chirality, including antibiotic compounds and many bacteriocins, with some exceptions (e.g., circular bacteriocins, leaderless peptides, T6SS pore-forming effectors). She concluded that their inherent resistance to many forms of predation could allow mirror bacteria to have very low death rates overall, enabling their populations to grow steadily, even with relatively low birth rates.

Prof. Agashe then envisioned what might happen if mirror bacteria escaped into natural environments. She argued that mirror bacteria could behave similarly to invasive species that lack predators and disrupt ecosystems, persisting even in environments not conducive to robust growth. From there, they could spread across terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems through wind, water, animals, and human transportation systems, leading to repeated introductions to many different environments. Meanwhile, mirror bacteria could evolve to consume additional nutrients, more effectively transport and metabolize nutrients, and/or resist abiotic stressors.

Prof. Agashe highlighted two ecosystem-level threats of particular concern: the loss of keystone species, which could destabilize food webs, alter primary habitats, and interrupt geochemical cycling, and the disruption of soil microbiota, which could alter nutrient cycling and availability and cause significant agricultural and ecological losses,

threaten food security, and further disrupt geochemical cycles.

Prof. Agashe then considered whether a mirror bacteria outbreak could realistically be contained. For natural-chirality invasive species, it typically takes years to identify an invasion, and effective removal measures are rarely available. Remediation after environmental introduction could be virtually impossible.

Prof. Agashe highlighted other potential countermeasures, such as developing novel enantiomeric antibiotics that target the appropriate chirality, engineering mirror phages designed to recognize the mirror bacteria, and germline engineering of plants and animals to recognize or defend against mirror bacteria. However, she argued that these countermeasures all face three key difficulties: they would only work locally, so distributing them globally would not be feasible, and mirror bacteria could evolve resistance to countermeasures just as natural pathogens do.

Remediation after environmental introduction could be virtually impossible.

Prof. Agashe summarized the ecological risks of mirror bacteria by stating that they could colonize and spread through various ecosystems, that animals and plants may be continuously exposed and create potentially severe effects on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, and that countermeasures would have limited efficacy.

Discussion highlights

On the question of nutrient availability and fitness cost, Prof. Agashe acknowledged that there is uncertainty around environmental nutrient profiles but that it is plausible that they are sufficient for the growth of mirror bacteria, especially in the likely context of low death rates.

When asked about mirror phages as a potential countermeasure, Prof. Agashe suggested that they would likely enter into an evolutionary arms race with mirror bacteria that might not lead to the extinction of either species. In later conversations, she clarified that mirror phages would be unlikely to reduce mirror bacterial populations enough to mitigate the potential for widespread and irreversible environmental harms.

Asked about potential environmental benefits of mirror organisms, Prof. Agashe mused that she had not considered the question in depth, but that she expects that mirror organisms would be unlikely to provide any benefit.

In considering how to communicate risks without undermining trust in science, Prof. Agashe suggested that collaborative dialogue on the responsible use of science will hopefully build rather than diminish trust.

Host Encounters with Mirror Bacteria

David Relman, MD, Stanford University

Prof. Relman's seminar focused on explaining the risks of mirror bacteria to the health of human, animal, and plant hosts, starting with exposure and entry to a human body. Natural-chirality bacteria often gain entry to hosts using specialized virulence factors. Because these virulence factors are chiral, their mirror-image forms in mirror bacteria would be unlikely to be effective. Nevertheless, mirror bacteria could enter hosts through other routes. Even in healthy individuals, natural-chirality commensal bacteria in the environment routinely translocate into tissues through ingestion, inhalation, and routine skin abrasions (e.g., brushing teeth); mirror bacteria would likely do the same.

Once inside of a human host, mirror bacteria could plausibly find ample sources of nutrients. Prof. Relman revisited Prof. Agashe's point regarding the

achiral nutrients that are minimally required for natural-chirality *E. coli* to grow. Natural-chirality *E. coli* requires roughly 100–1000 µg/L of achiral nutrients, which are not only available in ocean water (1–1000 µg/L) and soil (0.8–8 mg/L), but also in the human gut lumen (0.1–150 mg/L) and blood (0.1–180 mg/L). This implies that there may be sufficient nutrients for mirror bacteria to grow within the human body.²⁴

Prof. Relman then provided a deeper dive into how mirror bacteria could evade several central aspects of the immune system, including innate immune recognition, immune effector functions within the complement system, and adaptive immune defense.

Innate immunity relies on host pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), such as toll-like receptors (TLRs), to detect microbe-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs) and activate a variety of non-specific host responses to quickly counter microbial threats. However, these MAMPs all have chiral features, so PRRs would likely not recognize and respond to them properly in mirror bacteria. Prof. Relman referenced studies in TLR2-deficient mice, which succumb rapidly to common bacterial infections,²⁵ and children born without functioning IRAK-4 or MyD88 proteins, who experience ~40% mortality by age 8,²⁶ to illustrate how the absence of even a single functional immune pathway can be fatal.

Mirror bacteria could evade several central aspects of the immune system.

The complement system is composed of three primary pathways: the classical, alternative, and lectin pathways. Prof. Relman argued that the alternative pathway could remain active, but that the lectin pathway could be inactive and the classical pathway could be impaired because they both depend upon the interactions of chiral molecules. Once microbes are detected, immune

Figure 3: Mirror bacteria could evade multiple critical components of human immune defense due to incompatible chirality. Pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) may fail to detect mirror-image molecular patterns, complement pathways could be impaired, immune effector enzymes may be unable to degrade mirror-image proteins, and antigen presentation for adaptive immunity could be compromised.

systems deploy effectors like complement proteins and enzymes to clear them. Prof. Relman explained that many of these effectors also use chirality-dependent mechanisms to bind to a target and/or cleave its proteins. To support this, he shared experimental data demonstrating that the enzymes papain and elastase fail to degrade mirrored peptides.²⁷ Phagocytosis—the process by which immune cells engulf and destroy bacteria—could also be compromised against mirror bacteria because of the required stereospecific interactions.

Finally, Prof. Relman argued that the adaptive immune system could also be impaired against a mirror organism because it relies heavily on chiral upstream processes to present antigens to T cells. He shared experimental data demonstrating that certain mirror-image antigens did not activate T cells in mice, thus causing B cells to fail to produce antibodies.²⁸ T cell-independent pathways also rely on chiral PRRs to initiate inflammation. Children born with MHC-II deficiency (bare lymphocyte

syndrome), a defect in the production of a single antigen-presenting molecule, have a 100% mortality rate by age 10 without a bone marrow transplant; mirror bacterial infection could be functionally similar to a defect in the production of many such molecules.²⁹ Prof. Relman concluded that, taken together, the theoretical arguments and experimental evidence on mirror-image molecule recognition and genetic case studies of immunodeficiencies suggest that mirror bacteria may successfully evade major components of the immune system.

The pathology of mirror bacteria infection is unclear but could be fatal. Acute infections of the bloodstream may present as sepsis-like hyperinflammation, not triggered by the mirror bacteria directly, but later by damage to host tissue and the subsequent triggering of damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs). This could lead to organ failure and/or death, similar to severe bacterial infections in immunocompromised individuals. Chronic

infections meanwhile may be caused by the gradual accumulation of mirror bacteria within cells and lung, skin, or gut tissues, where they could compete for nutrients with host tissues and cause organ dysfunction over time.

Prof. Relman outlined how many existing medical countermeasures would likely be ineffective against mirror bacteria. Most antibiotics are chiral, so only a few classes of achiral or racemic antibiotics may work if the mirror bacteria happens to be susceptible to them, though they could evolve resistance. Current bacterial vaccines could be ineffective because they are directed at pathogen-specific chiral molecules. Mirror versions of most chemically-produced antibiotics could plausibly be manufactured relatively quickly, but it would be much more difficult to quickly produce mirror antibiotics through biosynthesis. Novel bacterial vaccines could theoretically be developed, but any new treatments could be exceptionally difficult to develop, test, manufacture, deploy, and distribute at a global scale. Developing rapid medical countermeasures to mirror bacteria would likely be far more difficult than developing and distributing the COVID-19 vaccine, which was already a massive global challenge.

In his concluding thoughts, Prof. Relman emphasized that animals and plants are at risk for similar reasons to humans—their structures are “leaky” and their immune systems rely on chiral immune mechanisms. He reiterated that, absent compelling evidence suggesting otherwise, mirror life should not be created, funders should make clear that they will not support mirror life creation, and there is a need for ongoing discussion.

Discussion highlights

Asked whether there should be any additional experimental research before proceeding with the recommendations called for in the *Science* paper, Prof. Relman emphasized the need to consider the

specific trade-offs of any given experiment. Ideally, any experimental research to characterize the risks of mirror life would help to answer the question of whether or not it should be created, as long as such research would not itself also facilitate or enable its creation.

Asked how poor health outcomes could occur without virulence factors, Prof. Relman reiterated that the absence of one mechanism for pattern recognition (e.g., MyD88 deficiency) can lead to fatal outcomes from pathogens that are not typically lethal to humans.

Prof. Relman was asked about the existence of opposition to the recommendations in the *Science* paper. He said that initially he and many of the other co-authors were skeptical, particularly about the feasibility of constructing a mirror organism and its overall fitness if it were created. However, as each author outlined the potential feasibility, countermeasures, and risks associated with their particular domain of expertise, the doubts of their counterparts were overcome.

Prof. Relman was asked whether disclosing the risks of mirror life constituted an information hazard. He acknowledged the possibility, but emphasized that research with the goal of creating mirror life was already being actively pursued and funded (e.g., via a 2019 U.S. NSF grant), that the global community now has the opportunity and time to stop it, and that it would already be difficult to pursue advances towards mirror life without being noticed.

Closing Remarks

David Relman & David Bikard

While acknowledging uncertainty around the risks of mirror life, Prof. Relman emphasized that they are plausible and serious enough to warrant immediate action. For most of his career, he said, he had been skeptical of ‘existential’ risk claims,

viewing them as overblown. But mirror life, in his view, is the first scenario in which he must acknowledge that such a risk is plausible.

Since the publication of the *Science* paper and technical report in December 2024, he said, the research community's response has been remarkably engaged and broadly in agreement that the risks of mirror life clearly outweigh the benefits. Prof. Relman offered his appreciation for those who had previously pursued mirror life but had since joined the effort to raise caution: "They have sacrificed their own research and personal goals and they could certainly be considered role models for this."

Prof. Relman stressed that the current moment represents a rare opportunity to identify and act on the risks of a technology before it becomes feasible. But he warned that the window is not indefinite. What worries him most, he said, is that the opportunity will be lost because of competing priorities or disagreement on how to act. This moment, he argued, is also a chance for scientists to demonstrate a willingness to accept limits. "With

this power that scientists have," he said, "comes responsibilities—and the acknowledgment of these responsibilities means to accept limits on that power." He suggested that principled restraint could help rebuild public trust in science at a time when that trust is under strain.

The current moment represents a rare opportunity to identify and act on the risks of a technology before it becomes feasible.

Prof. David Bikard followed with closing remarks from the perspective of the Institut Pasteur, offering a hopeful perspective. He reminded attendees of the extraordinary contributions that synthetic biology has already made to human health. Roughly 50% of new drugs brought to market today are products of recombinant DNA and genetic engineering. These benefits, he argued, show why the scientific enterprise must continue. But that pursuit, he emphasized, must be conducted responsibly.

Summary of Day 2: Workshops

Risk & Benefit Assessment of Mirror Life

Summary

The Risk & Benefit Assessment of Mirror Life workshop track brought together a group of 16 experts in microbiology, synthetic biology, microbial ecology, bioinformatics, biosecurity, epidemiology, food safety, astrobiology, and toxicology, as well as animal, invertebrate, and human immunology. The discussion focused on identifying and prioritizing areas for future research across four thematic areas: environmental spread; pathogenesis in humans, plants, and animals; human immune function and countermeasures; and potential benefits. The conversations in this track were also informed by a pre-conference virtual roundtable discussion on the same topics. This summary follows the chronology of major discussion topics but reorders some points for clarity.

Nearly the entire group agreed with the following statement: “Based on available evidence, the risks of building mirror bacteria far outweigh the plausible benefits, which can be largely achieved with alternative means. The international governance community should move forward with efforts to robustly prevent the creation of mirror bacteria.” One participant abstained from providing an opinion, and another disagreed with the statement and stated that governance efforts could be difficult to reverse and could be premature given the strength of the evidence.

The group also mostly agreed upon the following qualifications:

1. “We considered what results, data, or outputs from these lines of inquiry would change this perspective;
2. The group was unable to identify one or a small number of key experiments that would change this assessment in the near term;
3. We acknowledged the possibility of research that might reduce uncertainties for other stakeholders with roles in policy decision making; and
4. If additional research were to be considered, it should be done so in an open and transparent fashion, as should the conduct of that research and the sharing of the results.”

Environmental spread of mirror bacteria

The group began by brainstorming potential future research areas related to the environmental spread of mirror bacteria. Some initial suggestions included investigating disinfectants that could kill mirror bacteria while preserving natural-chirality life, conducting challenge experiments that expose multicellular organisms to natural-chirality vs. mirror-image versions of the same molecules, and attempting to estimate likely mutation rates of mirror bacteria. Additional ideas were raised periodically throughout the rest of the workshop.

The group was unable to identify one or a small number of key experiments that would change their risk-benefit assessment in the near term.

The group briefly discussed the potential use of AI models of environmental spread. Several participants cautioned against drawing conclusions informed by models that are trained on sparse or less relevant data. Even existing models of well-studied natural organisms can be unreliable

due to a lack of data, such as genotype to phenotype predictions for *E. coli*. However, one participant argued that rule-based AI, an approach that uses explicit logic rather than learned statistical patterns, could be applied to tools that identify risks or generate research hypotheses through structured reasoning.

One participant suggested a potential experiment to study the environmental survival and spread of mirror bacteria by reversing the chirality of both the bacteria and the environment. First, minimal natural-chirality bacteria would be engineered to have simple genomes and only basic metabolic functions, as a proxy for hypothetical newly-created mirror bacteria. The minimal natural-chirality bacteria would then be studied in artificial environments with many mirror-image nutrients but few natural-chirality nutrients, as a mirror-image proxy for the natural environment.

Another participant considered whether bacterial predators such as protists might mitigate the risk of environmental spread by ingesting initially fragile and slower growing mirror bacteria. However, others highlighted that because mirror bacteria would likely be indigestible, protists would not derive nutrients from these prey and their populations would not expand to be able to control growing mirror bacteria populations. To investigate this contention, the group brainstormed experiments to assess protists' ability to consume and metabolize mirror-image proteins. Such experiments could involve providing protists with access to bacteria or lipid vesicles loaded with exogenous labeled mirror-image proteins (compared to controls) and measuring effects on digestion, excretion, potential accumulation of the labeled proteins, reproductive rate, and other outcomes. Analogous experiments could allow researchers to study the fate of mirror-image proteins in immune phagocytic cells after phagocytosis.

Pathogenesis

The group discussed the course of infection by mirror organisms in humans, animals, and plants. Overall, there was agreement that additional experimental data would be helpful in verifying assumptions about how host immune systems would respond. While studies of immune deficiencies in humans have helped to understand the possible outcome of infection by mirror bacteria, similar data for invertebrates and plants are sparse. A few participants suggested that existing studies on human immune deficiencies are too few in number and context-dependent for direct extrapolation to mirror bacteria infection.

One participant suggested that environmental factors influencing the human immune system such as age, diet, behavior, geography, and the gut microbiome should be considered more carefully in the context of mirror bacterial infection. There was disagreement over whether these factors should be prioritized for further research; some felt that research on basic immune mechanisms within and across species would be more informative.

While studies of immune deficiencies in humans have helped to understand the possible outcome of infection by mirror bacteria, similar data for invertebrates and plants are sparse.

The group also discussed potential lessons from existing research into natural-chirality bacterial pathogenesis. Some participants noted that *E. coli* would be a likely candidate for an initial mirror strain, but that humans generally fail to generate a broadly protective adaptive immune response from vaccines against natural *E. coli* or natural pathogenic *E. coli* infections. *E. coli* infection already results in recurring colonization and harmful outcomes for immunocompromised individuals—a risk that could be shared by healthy individuals if

the immune response to mirror bacteria is impaired as expected.

Human immune function and countermeasures

The group moved on to discuss the challenges of designing experiments to investigate human immune reactions to mirror bacteria. A few participants highlighted that even if the innate immune system could recognize mirror-image versions of many molecules that act as canonical immune targets (e.g., lipopolysaccharides and peptidoglycan), a minimal mirror cell might be constructed to simply lack those molecules. Some mycoplasmas and related minimal cells already lack some of these molecules.

One participant raised several points related to archaea. They noted that unlike bacteria and eukaryotes, archaea contain lipids of opposite chirality in their membranes, so mirror archaea could plausibly function with natural-chirality lipids that might be recognized by the immune system. They also noted that some archaea lack peptidoglycan entirely, implying that it might be feasible to engineer a mirror cell without peptidoglycan.

The group considered ways to fill gaps in the immunological literature on mirror-image proteins. Current assumptions about human immune responses to mirror-image proteins are based on studies of a few mirror-image peptides and proteins. While a mirror bacterium would have hundreds or thousands of different proteins that could potentially be detectable, there are strong theoretical reasons to expect that the fundamental resistance to detection demonstrated in existing studies would extend to all mirror-image proteins. Still, it was suggested that many mirror-image proteins should be tested in both *in vivo* and *ex vivo* models for immunogenicity. Researchers could also better assess certain aspects of the potential

immune response to mirror bacteria by replicating existing studies on protease cleavage of mirror-image peptides with a large panel of proteins tested against a greater number of proteases over a longer timescale.

It was suggested that many mirror proteins should be tested in both *in vivo* and *ex vivo* models for immunogenicity.

Some participants expressed skepticism towards developing conjugate vaccines against mirror bacteria because no effective vaccines have been developed for natural *E. coli* or mycoplasmas. One participant argued that even recent immunogenic *E. coli* vaccines failed to prevent disease in Phase 3 clinical trials. Therefore, vaccine studies that use discrete mirror *E. coli* components to test immunogenicity in mice may not predict efficacy in humans or even indicate if a protective vaccine could be developed. Other therapeutic possibilities might include glycan-targeting vaccines and antibody therapies. However, even effective vaccines against disease can fail to prevent bacterial colonization, which, alongside the potential subsequent buildup of toxic byproducts or host cellular damage, could result in sepsis-like pathology. Another participant suggested that studying immune responses to individual mirror-image proteins might still yield useful insights to shape immune responses to mirror bacteria, even if developing an effective vaccine proves unattainable.

Another area of debate was over the possibility of chirality-independent immune pathways, such as glyco-conjugate interactions, and whether some mirror bacteria strains may be inherently “safer” than other mirror strains if they activated these pathways. Several participants questioned whether there were any lifeforms in which these pathways would be sufficient to trigger a robust immune response, considering the absence of other

expected deficiencies in recognition. After failing to identify any potential candidates, several members of the group argued that this line of research was fraught with risk. Even if a hypothetical strain of mirror bacteria were theoretically safer than others because it activated certain specific immune pathways, its creation could soon lead to the evolution or deliberate creation of strains that did not activate the same pathways.

Potential benefits

The group moved on to consider the potential benefits of mirror life, weigh them against the potential risks, and identify avenues that warranted further research. While the group did not dismiss the potential value of mirror organisms, several participants said that any claims must be scrutinized carefully and weighed against potential costs. One participant argued that any proposed benefit should be judged against a counterfactual of alternative research that could be achieved with the same time and resources that would otherwise be invested in creating mirror bacteria.

The group considered potential fundamental scientific benefits and practical benefits of mirror life. One participant discussed the potential for mirror organisms to produce mirror biomolecules more efficiently and cost-effectively than chemical synthesis, but they also expressed concern that if a mirror bacterium were created, economic incentives could lead companies to develop more robust strains that could pose greater biosecurity risks.

The group also discussed whether mirror life could offer potential benefits for studying the origins of homochirality or for defending against possible future threats such as naturally-occurring extraterrestrial mirror life. Some felt that such inquiries would either not be effectively addressed by mirror organisms or could be pursued using only mirror-image biomolecules. Overall, most of the

group agreed that it was unlikely there were any additional major potential benefits not yet identified.

Prioritization of research and participant reflections

After discussing future areas of potential research, the group attempted to prioritize these areas based on their current level of uncertainty, how feasible it would be to address them, and whether resolving uncertainty would substantively impact efforts to understand risks, develop countermeasures, respond to outbreaks, or develop governance.

The group agreed on four higher-priority research areas:

1. Environmental spread: Research into whether or how natural-chirality microbes could acquire the means to consume mirror-image biomolecules
2. Human immune function: Further research on immune receptor recognition of mirror-image components such as mirror-image proteins and lipids
3. Countermeasures: Research that clarifies the possibility of potentially effective countermeasures against mirror bacteria by examining the effectiveness of mirror-image or achiral molecules against natural chirality organisms
4. Potential benefits: Research on “assessing future capabilities and alternative approaches for mirror-image biomolecule manufacturing”

Toward the end of the workshop, participants considered the following statement:

“Based on available evidence, the risks of building mirror bacteria far outweigh the plausible benefits, which can be largely achieved with alternative means. The international governance

community should move forward with efforts to robustly prevent the creation of mirror bacteria.”

Through an informal vote, 12 out of 14 participants agreed with the statement, with one abstention and one dissent (two participants left the workshop early). Several participants noted the importance of including the phrase “based on the available evidence” to ensure flexibility as additional data and information are acquired through new research. The dissenting participant expressed concern about the potential difficulty of resuming research funding and potential erosion of public trust if evidence suggesting minimal risks of mirror organisms came to light.

The group also mostly agreed upon and provided the following qualifications for the statement above:

1. “We considered what results, data, or outputs from these lines of inquiry would change this perspective;
2. The group was unable to identify one or a small number of key experiments that would change this assessment in the near term;
3. We acknowledged the possibility of research that might reduce uncertainties for other stakeholders with roles in policy decision making; and
4. If additional research were to be considered, it should be done so in an open and transparent fashion, as should the conduct of that research and the sharing of the results.”

Cross-track discussion

During a cross-track debrief among participants from all five workshop tracks, the group further elaborated on the risks of mirror life and potential benefits of mirror-image biomolecules. One participant from another track asked whether the “Risk & Benefit Assessment” group had discussed the potential benefits of mirror-image biomolecules in greater detail; another participant answered that there had only been a brief discussion and that it was difficult to quantify the potential benefits (the benefits of mirror-image biomolecules were discussed extensively in the *Technical Feasibility and Development Pathways* track). Another participant suggested that more sophisticated risk-assessment frameworks such as real options theory could be used to estimate the value of further research in reducing uncertainty about risks and benefits.

In a separate thread of discussion, one participant raised the possibility that the natural environment could contain compounds that would be toxic to mirror organisms. In response, another participant noted that this possibility could be empirically investigated without creating mirror life by studying its converse: whether mirror-image versions of abundant natural compounds would be toxic to natural-chirality life.* Another participant noted that a malicious actor could simply engineer or evolve a mirror organism to be resistant to any particular toxic compound.

**One reviewer of this report noted that this topic is covered in Box 1.2 in the technical report⁶ accompanying the 2024 Science paper.⁵*

Technical Feasibility and Development Pathways

Summary

The Technical Feasibility and Development Pathways workshop track discussed current and potential future milestones towards the creation of mirror life and their potential as areas for governance. The 16 participants included experts in biochemistry, biosecurity, molecular engineering, and synthetic biology. The discussion was also informed by a pre-conference virtual roundtable on the development of mirror life with a partially overlapping group of experts. Summary points refer to the in-person group unless otherwise noted.

The in-person group focused mostly on “bottom-up” pathways to creating mirror life because the prior virtual roundtable participants judged them to be more feasible in the near term than “top-down” pathways. The in-person discussion spanned mirror-image protein synthesis, genome assembly, translation systems, and potential booting platforms. While views differed on timelines and priorities, participants in both the virtual and in-person groups agreed that creating mirror life would be feasible in the future but is not possible with current technologies.

Participants agreed that the following were key technical milestones towards the creation of mirror life and discussed their potential as areas for governance:

1. A fully synthetic natural-chirality or mirror-image ribosome.
2. A fully-defined, successfully “booted” synthetic natural-chirality cell.
3. An *in vitro* synthetic mirror-image genome.
4. A natural-chirality “Protein synthesis Using Recombinant Elements” (PURE) system (a cell-free protein synthesis system composed of

isolated proteins, ribosomes, tRNAs, and chemicals) that is efficient enough to be self-sustaining.

Participants generally considered the first two milestones to be more difficult achievements than the latter two. There was disagreement about whether or not a mirror-image ribosome should be pursued, and many felt that fully-defined synthetic cell booting was not a priority in the synthetic biology community and may be a promising stopping point for research. Many participants also believed that a self-sustaining PURE system would be less dangerous than a mirror-image ribosome and that its development should be permitted.

Some also argued that if it were feasible to construct, a “crossover” natural-chirality ribosomal translation system that could produce mirror-image proteins could be a less risky alternative to a mirror-image ribosome, though it would also enable top-down and bottom-up pathways to creating mirror life by allowing for easier production of mirror-image proteins.

Synthesizing mirror-image biomolecules and cellular components

There was general agreement in the virtual group that in the near future, “bottom-up” pathways to creating mirror life appeared more technically feasible than “top-down” pathways, leading the in-person group to focus primarily on bottom-up pathways. The group reviewed the current and near-term feasibility of creating mirror life by assembling it from mirror-image versions of key biomolecules and cellular components: DNA, RNA, proteins, ribosomes, translation platforms, and synthetic compartments. One participant argued that synthesizing a mirror-image cell membrane would not be a significant challenge, and the topic was not discussed further. Another argued that a

minimal mirror cell that could not make its own amino acids, nucleic acids, fatty acids, lipids, and cofactors would, in itself, pose no risk because it could not survive unless all of these mirror-image molecules were provided in its growth media, but that such a minimal cell could serve as a chassis on which to construct a dangerous mirror organism with relatively little difficulty.

Mirror-image nucleic acids and genomes

Participants in the in-person group discussed the state of chemically synthesizing mirror-image nucleic acids and the process of assembling a full mirror-image genome. They considered how this could be accomplished via a combination of chemical synthesis and Gibson Assembly, an *in vitro* DNA assembly method that uses a set of enzymes to seamlessly assemble fragments of DNA. To adapt Gibson Assembly methods to mirror-image DNA, mirror-image versions of three key enzymes are necessary: a mirror-image polymerase, ligase, and exonuclease. The synthesis of both a mirror-image polymerase and a mirror-image ligase has been achieved, leaving only the mirror-image exonuclease to be synthesized. It was noted that this could be achieved within one or two years with sufficient funding.

The group discussed how standard chemical synthesis methods can be used to produce mirror-image oligonucleotides (i.e., L-oligos, or short strands of mirror-image nucleic acids). Subsequently, kilobase-length mirror-image DNA can be produced by joining L-oligos via ligation with mirror-image DNA ligases and amplified through mirror-image polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with a mirror-image DNA polymerase. Participants agreed that while the synthesis of L-oligos is expensive, this cost is expected to decrease to a significant extent if demand for L-oligos increases and the processes used to create them are refined.

Overall, there was general agreement in both the virtual roundtable and the in-person group that *in*

vitro mirror-image genome synthesis is feasible with existing technologies and could be accomplished within a few years if attempted with sufficient resources.

Mirror-image ribosomes

Both the virtual and in-person groups widely agreed that the creation of a mirror-image ribosome would be a key technical milestone toward the creation of mirror life. Several participants strongly believed that it was by far the most difficult and important step.

The in-person group discussed the current state of the art in natural-chirality ribosome synthesis/reconstitution. If a natural-chirality ribosome could be assembled entirely without cell-derived components, the process could be recreated in mirror-image form to create a mirror-image ribosome. However, current methods of reconstituting natural-chirality ribosomes require cell-derived components, and they therefore cannot be applied to create a mirror-image ribosome without already having access to a mirror cell. Biologically active ribosomes are routinely reconstituted from cell lysate, reconstitution of functional ribosomes from largely recombinant proteins is possible, but cell-derived extracts are still required to provide some components such as ribosomal RNA (rRNA). Ribosomal RNA typically undergoes a range of base modifications, ribosomal proteins receive post-translational modifications, and the exact requirements for recreating these modifications are still inadequately understood. Researchers also currently lack a clear understanding of the correct ratios of these components. The creation of a fully synthetic natural-chirality ribosome therefore remains an active area of research.

Participants noted that reconstituted ribosomes vary widely in their efficiency. Ribosomal RNA and proteins typically require complex post-translational modifications for the resulting

ribosome to efficiently polymerize amino acids. An initial mirror-image ribosome lacking these modifications would thus likely have lower efficiency than its natural-chirality counterpart. Some participants in the in-person group suggested that a low-efficiency mirror-image ribosome could potentially serve as a stopping point for research because it could still significantly outperform chemical synthesis in the production of practically useful mirror-image proteins while still being inadequate for a functional mirror organism. However, others argued that a low-efficiency mirror-image ribosome could easily be used as a starting point for iterative improvement to a high-efficiency version that would be sufficient to create a mirror organism.

Both the virtual and in-person groups widely agreed that the creation of a mirror-image ribosome would be a key technical milestone toward the creation of mirror life.

Mirror-image ribosomes could potentially hold some practical value for the creation of useful mirror-image peptides and proteins. Certain mirror-image peptides and proteins have scientific and therapeutic applications, but they cannot currently be biomanufactured inside of cells because of their reversed chirality; instead, they are chemically synthesized. Some participants noted that chemical synthesis becomes increasingly inefficient and costly as the length and complexity of the peptides and proteins increases, and some argued that a mirror-image ribosome could enable higher-fidelity production of larger and more complex mirror-image proteins.

There was disagreement about whether the scientific and practical benefits of creating a mirror-image ribosome outweighed the risks. The in-person group did not extensively discuss the extent to which projected improvements in

chemical synthesis methods could be sufficient to meet practical demands for mirror-image peptides and proteins, but some members of the virtual group argued that substantial improvements in chemical synthesis and purification were likely in the near future.

While participants in both groups differed in their assessments of the timeline, difficulty, and value of creating a mirror-image ribosome, there was general agreement that it would eventually become feasible and that it would be a key enabling technology for mirror life. One participant in the in-person group posited that because mirror-image rRNA and proteins can now be synthesized, the reconstitution of a natural-chirality ribosome from fully synthetic components is the only major remaining technical barrier preceding the creation of a mirror-image ribosome. Because of this, several participants considered whether further research into reconstituting a natural-chirality ribosome should not be pursued. Others contended that the benefits of this research still outweighed potential risks, arguing that it could be useful for the production of a range of interesting molecules, and that creating a synthetic natural-chirality ribosome would inform scientists' basic understanding of its mechanisms and potentially enable useful new types of biosynthesis.

Orthogonal and crossover translation systems

Several participants in the in-person group discussed the possibility of re-engineering a natural-chirality ribosome to polymerize D-amino acids into mirror-image proteins and deploy it in a natural-chirality cell as part of an *in vivo* orthogonal translation system. An orthogonal translation system is engineered to operate independently of and in parallel to native cell machinery, allowing the incorporation of non-canonical amino acids into proteins. This approach of developing a “crossover ribosome” was seen as a way to develop a “crossover translation system” to synthesize

mirror-image proteins *in vivo* without the creation of mirror life. The concept gained traction during the discussion as a technically plausible and potentially lower-risk alternative to pursuing a mirror-image ribosome. However, it was pointed out that a crossover translation system is a key milestone in the top-down approach to creating mirror life, and crossover translation could be used *in vitro* or *in vivo* to synthesize mirror-image proteins for bottom-up mirror cell assembly. The group also considered the possibility that unforeseen interactions between the natural and mirror-image parts of a hybrid cell could lead to the creation of intermediate cell types that are likely to survive in a natural environment, thereby creating a risk of uncontrollable spread.

It was noted that a crossover translation system, whether *in vitro* or *in vivo*, would be very challenging to develop and not all participants were certain it was feasible. Some participants felt that it was still worth pursuing because a crossover ribosome could disincentivize the creation of mirror cells as a means to produce mirror-image proteins, and because synthetic cells with a crossover translation system would by definition have natural-chirality components that could potentially be recognized and attacked by host immune systems.

Booting synthetic cells from synthetic components

“Booting” a synthetic cell refers to the process of combining a genome, transcription–translation system, and membrane in such a way that initiates protein production and other life-like functions. A successful boot of a synthetic cell has not yet been reported in the literature, but it remains an active area of research. Participants in the in-person group discussed the technical milestone of booting natural-chirality synthetic cells and debated the extent to which it could facilitate the development

of mirror life. While there was no consensus on timelines, there was general agreement that, depending on the booting method used and the components involved, booting natural-chirality synthetic cells would be a critical milestone toward the development of mirror life.

The in-person group considered two different methods of booting synthetic natural-chirality cells: cell lysate booting and “fully-defined” booting. Cell lysate booting involves booting a genome that is supplied with lysate, the cytoplasmic contents of another living cell that are collected after rupturing its membrane. The precise contents of the lysate and their functions would be unknown, but the lysate would be expected to contain a sufficient set of biochemical components for booting a cell. In contrast, fully-defined booting involves supplying a genome with a specific set of defined biochemical components that are necessary and sufficient for booting. These components would likely be a superset of PURE (Protein synthesis Using Recombinant Elements) systems—cell-free protein synthesis systems that reconstitute the essential parts of translation machinery from purified components.

Booting natural-chirality synthetic cells would be a critical milestone toward the development of mirror life.

The group agreed that fully-defined booting would be much more difficult than lysate booting. One participant noted that fully synthetic protein synthesis systems tend to have much lower activity than cell-derived systems, and some participants were uncertain about whether fully-defined booting would even be achievable. The group also agreed that fully-defined booting would be more enabling than lysate booting for the creation of mirror life because once the necessary components for booting were known, it would be relatively easy to synthesize their mirror-image versions to boot up a

mirror cell. Closing out the discussion, the group agreed that fully-defined booting was not a priority within the synthetic biology community and that it may therefore represent a promising stopping point for research. This position was later questioned during a subsequent cross-track Q&A session (see below).

Self-sustaining PURE systems

One area of discussion among the group was whether a (natural-chirality) PURE system could be made self-sustaining, or capable of reproducing all of its own components. (As the term “PURE” was used in this context, all components required for biological protein synthesis would be produced individually, then mixed and assembled to make up a functional expression system.) Self-sustaining PURE could plausibly be used for fully-defined booting of a synthetic cell of either chirality. Several participants argued that self-sustaining PURE is not currently possible because it must be capable of de novo ribosome biogenesis and assembly, as well as the synthesis of many proteins with still unknown structures, some of which may also require unidentified chaperone proteins to properly fold and function. However, there was general agreement that creating a self-sustaining PURE system is an empirical problem that could be solved by trial and error. If a self-sustaining natural-chirality PURE system could be developed, then it would likely also be possible to develop a self-sustaining mirror-image PURE system, which could enable the booting of mirror cells.

Ultimately, most participants agreed that because the reconstitution of natural-chirality ribosomes remains one of the most significant technical milestones towards creating mirror life because it is likely a key precursor technology for mirror-image ribosome reconstitution, self-sustaining PURE, and mirror-image PURE. Many participants also agreed that self-sustaining PURE should be permitted and

that it would not facilitate the creation of mirror life as much as a mirror-image ribosome.

Additional governance considerations

The in-person group briefly discussed how to monitor and potentially regulate the technologies discussed above without unnecessarily constraining research. Some noted a distinction between control of information and control of physical materials. For example, creating a mirror-image genome would not require substantial new information, but it would require a substantial set of mirror-image nucleic acids that could in theory be regulated. Conversely, creating a mirror-image ribosome would not require as much molecular material as a mirror-image genome, but it would require significant additional technical progress. Participants in both the virtual and in-person groups also noted the difficulty of defining clear thresholds for many aspects of biological activity, including self-replication, functional protein synthesis efficiency, and genome functionality.

The in-person group agreed that while they generally focused their discussion on a hypothetical mirror-image version of an existing bacterium such as *E. coli*, alternative cell-like mirror systems (e.g., a mirror version of a fully synthetic minimal cell) could carry similar risks, particularly if they would make it easier to subsequently create other forms of mirror life.

Several participants also encouraged further open discussions about research with the potential to enable the creation of mirror life and its precursor technologies among a broader group of stakeholders. Others suggested that funders could play a key role by declining to fund research that may approach key milestones. Several also emphasized the need to work with policymakers to support regulations in the best interest of society, even if it limits their own research ambitions. Both

the virtual and in-person groups endorsed the goal of preserving the benefits of related research to the extent possible.

Cross-track discussion

During a cross-track debrief among participants from all five workshop tracks, the in-person group discussed the potential to draw boundaries around the precursor technologies for mirror life discussed above. There was continued disagreement about whether a mirror-image ribosome should be pursued; some participants argued that it could provide value for the construction of large mirror-image proteins compared with chemical synthesis, but many agreed that it would also significantly enable the creation of mirror organisms. One participant argued that given the severity of the risk, it would be prudent to draw multiple independent regulatory boundaries to prevent the creation of mirror life.

There was also additional discussion of creating a crossover ribosome that could construct mirror-image proteins based on genetic information from a natural-chirality genome. One participant raised the concern that a crossover ribosome could disincentivize the pursuit of mirror life through the “bottom-up” pathway while enabling it through the “top-down” pathway. (One reviewer of this report also raised the concern that a crossover ribosome could enable both pathways simply by making it easier to produce mirror-image proteins at scale.)

Finally, one participant questioned the viability of defining a stopping point for research at fully-defined natural-chirality synthetic cell booting. The participant argued that such an accomplishment would have significant scientific value, that some laboratories are already likely to soon achieve fully defined synthetic cell booting with recombinant proteins, and that it might not be feasible to stop them.

Preparedness and Countermeasures

Summary

In the Preparedness and Countermeasures workshop track, 17 life scientists, biosafety and biosecurity experts, and policy advisors examined strategies for protecting against potential threats from mirror bacteria. The goals of the track were to assess the feasibility of containment, detection, and countermeasure efforts that do not themselves advance the development of mirror bacteria. The conversations in this track were also informed by a pre-conference virtual roundtable discussion on the same topics, organized by the meeting conveners, which included some of the workshop participants as well as other nominees who were not able to attend. The summary includes notes from a pre-conference virtual roundtable where appropriate.

There was broad agreement among the group on the following points:

1. Based on current knowledge, there is no plausible way that current or future countermeasures could mitigate an acceptable fraction of the risks from mirror bacteria.
2. The group could not envision any potential future countermeasures that would fully eradicate mirror bacteria from the environment.
3. Research into countermeasures does not require facilitating the creation of mirror organisms, and research that does so should not be performed.
4. If countries pursue countermeasures development, they should do so in a collaborative and transparent fashion to avoid triggering geopolitical security issues.
5. There are no known physical or biological containment strategies that could fully secure mirror bacteria against deliberate release.
6. Scaling and implementing detection systems and countermeasures for mirror bacteria would be a major challenge.
7. General-purpose preparedness measures such as protective equipment and disinfection systems could play a role in reducing human exposure to mirror bacteria.

Containment

The group discussed the feasibility of physical and biological containment of mirror bacteria. One participant proposed engineering mirror organisms to be dependent on multiple synthetic nutrients that are absent from nature, which could safeguard against environmental survival. Another participant suggested that the dependencies could be tested on synthetic normal-chirality organisms in the near term. However, the group raised concerns about the durability of such containment, citing risks of horizontal gene transfer, metabolic adaptation, human error, and the possibility that mirror bacteria could evolve around engineered dependencies in large populations. Technicians could also deliberately remove dependencies with similar tools to those that were used to add them.

The group also extensively discussed risks stemming from the inadequacy of physical containment measures. They highlighted structural limitations in existing biosafety infrastructure, with one participant arguing that BSL-4 laboratories are designed for viruses and not bacteria. Natural disasters or military strikes could also result in the unintentional release of mirror bacteria from laboratories. One participant emphasized that stronger empirical evidence of the difficulty of perfect physical containment would further improve the case for caution.

More broadly, the group identified deliberate misuse as the most serious failure mode for

containment. They were unable to identify any physical or biocontainment strategy that could fully prevent the intentional release of mirror organisms, whether from an insider threat or an independent effort to develop and deliberately release them. Even with future tools like robotic laboratory automation, humans would still be required for maintenance, oversight, and transferring materials out of containment facilities, creating ongoing vulnerabilities to both intentional misuse and accidental breaches.

The group was unable to identify any physical or biocontainment strategy that could fully prevent the intentional release of mirror organisms.

Detection

The group discussed the practical challenges of implementing detection systems for mirror organisms. Several participants emphasized the need for clear response protocols and noted that developing and deploying effective detection technologies at scale, even for existing pandemic pathogens, is extremely costly and difficult. In particular, intellectual property rights and export controls may be significant potential barriers for deploying detection systems, particularly in crisis scenarios where rapid deployment is essential.

Participants explored the feasibility of developing mirror-image analogues of existing detection technologies. One participant proposed constructing inverted PCR systems using mirror-image polymerases, which have already been developed.^{20,30,31} Inverted PCR could have potential for highly specific detection because the absence of naturally-occurring mirror-image DNA in the environment would result in virtually no background noise. Additional detection strategies could include the use of L-glucose agar plates as environmental sensors, where only mirror bacteria

would be capable of growth, as well as light microscopy, Raman spectroscopy, and mass spectrometry. One virtual roundtable participant suggested the use of AI systems to monitor research publications for advances towards mirror life.

The group generally agreed that it would be valuable to establish baseline environmental readings to verify the absence of mirror-image biological material. Participants favored detection systems that could be deployed proactively, likening their role to Geiger counters in radiation safety that offer constant early-warning monitoring before and during exposure events.

Medical countermeasures

Both the virtual pre-conference group and the in-person group discussed several types of medical countermeasures, focusing primarily on antibiotics. Most current antibiotics are chiral and are thus unlikely to be effective against mirror bacteria. Participants in both groups noted several possible types of antibiotics that may be effective: existing achiral and racemic antibiotics, mirror-image versions of existing antibiotics, and new broad-spectrum antibiotics targeting biological features unique to mirror organisms. New antibiotics would need safety testing before deployment, and all antibiotics would need efficacy testing against mirror bacteria.

The in-person group also agreed on the inadequacy of existing vaccine approaches against mirror bacteria and discussed possible novel approaches. Typical vaccines function by exposing the immune system to molecules from pathogens in order to prepare it to respond effectively in the future, but this method would not be effective if the immune system is unable to effectively recognize mirror-image molecules. To address the issue, one participant proposed developing triconjugate or peptide-conjugate vaccines that allow the immune

system to recognize mirror organisms by conjugating mirror-image antigens to normal-chirality carriers. However, the group did not extensively discuss the feasibility of this approach. (In addition, participants in the “Risk & Benefit Assessment of Mirror Life” track expressed skepticism about the efficacy of conjugate vaccines against mirror bacteria because no effective vaccines have been developed for natural *E. coli* or mycoplasmas.)

One participant proposed an experimental gene therapy approach designed as a prophylactic treatment to reprogram the human immune system to detect mirror organisms. This approach would involve creating synthetic receptors and antibodies targeted at distinctive molecular patterns that would be expected in mirror-image proteins. Some saw promise in this strategy, while others cautioned that using it during an active infection could trigger an overwhelming immune response that could be fatal to the user.

Both the virtual pre-conference group and the in-person group raised serious concerns about the feasibility of producing and scaling medical countermeasures for ongoing widespread use. They emphasized fundamental scaling challenges, noting that most high-grade antibiotics require sterile injection manufacturing with complex global supply chains that would be extremely difficult to scale rapidly during a crisis. Participants in both groups also noted that mirror bacterial countermeasures would likely require continuous administration rather than one-time dosing, compounding logistical and manufacturing challenges. Several participants were concerned about the difficulty of gaining preemptive regulatory approval for countermeasures targeting a hypothetical threat, as well as difficulties with international coordination and equity in access. Participants in both groups cited the delayed regulatory uptake of PCR diagnostics for smallpox

detection and the stark disparities in global access to vaccines and treatments during COVID-19, both of which were responses to existing threats. They argued that rallying support, gaining regulatory approval, and ensuring equitable distribution for countermeasures against a hypothetical future risk would be exponentially more difficult, making effective deployment even less likely.

Overall, many members of the virtual and in-person groups agreed that while future medical countermeasures may be feasible, their implementation would face massive logistical and regulatory hurdles, and they would offer no protection for plants, animals, and ecosystems, as discussed in the next section.

Both the virtual pre-conference group and the in-person group raised serious concerns about the feasibility of producing and scaling medical countermeasures for ongoing widespread use.

Agricultural and ecological countermeasures

Next, the in-person group discussed potential countermeasures for mitigating mirror bacterial threats to agriculture and the environment. They considered traditional agricultural disease control methods, including crop rotations, eliminating alternative hosts, removing infected plants, and soil decontamination through solarization, steam treatment, or chemical disinfection. Participants agreed that these approaches would likely fail due to the enormous scale required for effective implementation and the potential for mirror bacteria to persist in soil.

One participant proposed three potential ecological countermeasures. The first was to use mirror phages as biological control agents. Phages are

viruses that are capable of infecting bacteria; mirror phages could hypothetically be constructed and released at scale to infect and kill mirror bacteria in the environment. The second approach was to modify resistance genes such as XA21 from rice to detect mirror-image proteins and thus confer resistance in staple crops like rice, wheat, corn, and soy. The third was to re-engineer normal bacteria to act as predators for mirror bacteria by giving them the ability to degrade mirror-image proteins, with these bacteria potentially spreading their capability to other microbes through horizontal gene transfer.

The group discussed the limitations and implementation challenges of each of the proposed ecological countermeasures. Mirror phages would require mirror bacteria to replicate and thus depend on their hosts for survival, rendering complete eradication of mirror bacteria impossible. Several participants noted that biocontrol strategies can significantly reduce populations but have never succeeded in fully eradicating an invasive species. Regarding engineered plant resistance, the group acknowledged that a wide range of critical plant species in addition to key crops could be threatened and that it would be infeasible to identify and protect them all. The group did not extensively discuss reengineering normal bacteria. Many participants also expressed concern that properly testing novel ecological countermeasures could necessitate creating mirror bacteria, which they strongly opposed.

Uncertainties remained about some of the details of ecological risk. One participant expressed uncertainty around plants' vulnerability to mirror bacteria, noting that while mirror bacteria could plausibly colonize roots and stomata, their capacity to penetrate the phloem and cause systemic damage remains unclear. Another participant noted that the natural predators of bacteria would eventually evolve the ability to consume mirror-image biomass. However, the group agreed

that even if agricultural controls were effective or predators evolved to consume mirror bacteria, the initial phase of unchecked growth could plausibly inflict irreversible ecological damage.

Responsible approaches to countermeasures development

The group ended the workshop with a discussion of how to pursue preparedness measures while avoiding actions that could trigger international security dilemmas or inadvertently accelerate the development of mirror bacteria. Many noted that countermeasures research does not require facilitating the creation of mirror organisms. For example, studies of cross-chiral molecular interactions and in-silico modeling of drug-target dynamics could inform the development of medical countermeasures without directly enabling the development of mirror life.

Some participants argued that general-purpose protective equipment and built-environment control measures could also partially mitigate the risks of mirror bacteria without enabling their development, even though plants, animals, and ecosystems would still be at risk of exposure. Stockpiling and deploying equipment such as masks, germicidal lighting, filtration units, and disinfectants that work through achiral mechanisms was seen as a global priority. Distributing open-source technical instructions for deploying non-pharmaceutical measures could protect humans against a wide range of current and future pathogens. Some participants preferred these interventions over specialized pharmaceuticals because of their broad applicability, regulatory simplicity, and their reduced risk of triggering security dilemmas.

Participants in both the pre-conference group and the in-person group agreed that some countermeasures development could trigger security dilemmas if it was misperceived as

evidence of offensive mirror life research. Drawing on historical analogies, including secret biological weapons programs and Cold War misperceptions, one participant noted that secrecy has historically fueled worst-case thinking and arms races between nations. Several participants emphasized that it would be important to clearly state in public fora that mirror bacteria should not be pursued and that any research into countermeasures should be conducted collaboratively and transparently. Some suggested international cooperation mechanisms modeled on climate governance "club structures" that incentivize participation while creating soft deterrents against unilateral action.

Finally, one participant in the in-person group emphasized that effective preparedness requires sustained investment in human knowledge and institutional capacity. The group agreed with this sentiment, noting the importance of training the next generation of researchers and practitioners while preserving and operationalizing lessons from One Health, the Ebola response, and biological weapons governance to ensure that expertise and institutional memory are maintained for future preparedness efforts.

Principles for the Path Forward

Summary

In the Principles for the Path Forward workshop track, a group of 17 life scientists, social scientists, policy experts, and bioethicists discussed candidate principles for moving forward in addressing potential risks from mirror life. The group discussed historical case studies with potential relevance for mirror life, potential principles that could guide future governance efforts, and ideas for engaging a wider range of stakeholders. The conversations in this track were also informed by a pre-conference virtual roundtable discussion on the same topics which included some of the workshop participants as well as others who were not able to attend.

There was broad agreement on several principles to guide future efforts, given current scientific understanding. The exact phrasing of some principles was refined by the meeting chairs afterward and is provided below, and original versions are provided at the beginning of the “Potential principles” section:

1. “The creation of mirror life should be indefinitely prohibited.”
2. “The governance of the precursor technologies for mirror life must be sufficient to prevent its creation.”
3. “International cooperation is required to determine how best to govern the precursor technologies for mirror life.”
4. “Stakeholders other than scientists need to be involved in decision making about mirror life and related precursor technologies, including governments and civil society groups.”
5. “To the extent possible, the governance of mirror life and related precursor technologies should also preserve the benefits of biotechnology research.”

Comparing mirror life to historical case studies

The meeting chairs provided working definitions of several terms for use in the meeting:

1. **Principles:** Plain-language normative statements with words like “should” or “must” to guide the development of governance of mirror life and its precursor technologies. As used here, principles are intended to bridge the gap between broad ethical values, like fairness or respect for life, and specific policy proposals.
2. **Governance:** The rules and norms through which public affairs are managed.¹⁶
3. **Mirror life:** Self-replicating organisms in which all biomolecules have reversed chirality.
4. **Enabling or Precursor technologies:** Technologies that substantially aid the creation of mirror life.

The workshop track then began with discussion of four historical case studies of global governance of emerging technologies, which were chosen to invite discussion of potential principles for the governance of mirror organisms. The case studies were:

- **The Montreal Protocol (1987):** A global treaty to phase out the use of ozone-depleting substances. Considered successful due to clear science, strong enforcement, and international cooperation.
- **Restrictions on human cloning (~2004):** A collection of international and national policies responding to ethical concerns about human cloning. International efforts have lacked global consensus or binding enforcement; nevertheless, no full-term human reproductive cloning is known to have occurred.

- **Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty (NPT) (1968):** A cornerstone arms control treaty aiming to prevent the spread of nuclear weapons while promoting disarmament.
- **Biological Weapons Convention (BWC) (1975):** The first multilateral agreement banning an entire class of weapons of mass destruction, though weakened by lack of verification measures.

The group considered the applicability of these examples to the case of mirror life. One participant argued that mirror organisms are potentially unique in their potential for harm to humanity and ecosystems and that frameworks for preventing their creation must be correspondingly firm. Another cautioned against applying a “dual-use” framing to mirror organisms, given their apparent lopsided ratio of risk to potential benefit, and suggested that a dual-use framing could risk normalizing limited peaceful development of mirror organisms.

Several participants expressed interest in adapting existing regulations to the issue of mirror life. One suggested examining the WHO’s International Health Regulations as a source of inspiration. Others suggested adapting the BWC’s “general purpose criterion,” which governs biological and chemical agents based on their purpose as opposed to their origin or method of production, but there was disagreement about whether it would be politically productive to frame the issue of mirror life in relation to the BWC. The Tianjin Biosecurity Guidelines were also noted as a potential model for a declaration on mirror life; though not formally affiliated with the BWC, the Guidelines are closely aligned with its objectives and have been actively promoted within its framework. Another participant brought up the “precautionary principle,” a general principle of caution in the face of uncertain risks of substantial harm, though this principle has been criticized for

implicitly favoring a status quo that might itself be causing ongoing harm.

Several participants also expressed interest in “negative case studies” of governance failures. One participant brought up the work of researcher He Jiankui, who modified human embryos in the face of normative and regulatory barriers, as an example. Relatedly, one participant argued that case studies can be useful not only as evidence for general principles, but as examples of unexpected and historically contingent outcomes, and recommended caution, humility, and a willingness to listen to different perspectives when developing plans for governance.

Potential principles for the path forward

As a starting point for discussion, the meeting facilitators shared the following potential principles with the group, which were previously developed in a pre-conference virtual roundtable meeting:

1. “Mirror life should not be created unless future research convincingly demonstrates that it would not pose severe risks.”
2. “International collaboration is needed to determine the path forward.”
3. “Stakeholders other than scientists need to be involved in decision making, including governments and civil society groups.”
4. “To the extent possible, the governance of mirror life and related enabling technologies should also preserve the benefits of synthetic biology research.”
5. “The governance of mirror life and related enabling technologies must be sufficient to keep mirror life out of reach of malicious actors.”

Both the pre-conference virtual roundtable group and the in-person workshop group agreed with the

underlying ideas of the draft principles, and the discussion mainly focused on refining the wording to improve their accuracy and practical utility. Some in-person participants proposed variations in the wording of some principles—for example, phrases like “the governance of mirror life” might mistakenly convey that mirror life already exists to be governed, and the phrase “malicious actors” in principle 5 was criticized for implying a presumption that the intent of actors could be fully known or that non-malicious but irresponsible actors were not also of concern. One participant in the pre-conference meeting preferred the term “mirror-image life,” arguing that it has been standard for decades. Some participants were also concerned that the clause starting with “unless” in principle 1 risked creating an opening for future stakeholders to cite flawed research and proceed with developing mirror organisms. Others argued that it was important to retain such a clause to allow for the possibility that future research could change risk/benefit assessments.

The in-person group also discussed how to conceptualize the “enabling technologies” noted in principles 4 and 5. Several participants noted that the definitions of enabling technologies could be made arbitrarily broad and so required clarification. One participant suggested using “components” instead of “technologies,” which connotes physical elements that would be combined to create a mirror organism, as opposed to conceptual innovations. However, others noted that “lateral adjacencies” in other fields such as synthetic cell development could produce important conceptual innovations for the development of mirror organisms that were not simply components. To avoid confusion in the future, several members of the group recommended developing a shared glossary to clarify key terms.

In response to the discussion, one participant suggested a set of revised and incomplete potential

principles, acknowledging a need for additional rewording:

1. “The creation of mirror life should be indefinitely prohibited/postponed.”
2. “Governance of mirror life components must be sufficient to prevent the creation of mirror life.”
3. “International cooperation is required to determine governance mechanisms.”

The chair asked the room if anyone objected to any of these principles; there were no objections.

The pre-conference and in-person groups also considered whether any additional principles were needed. Participants in the pre-conference group suggested a potential principle of international transparency, and both groups emphasized the importance of distinguishing between mirror-image molecular biology and self-replicating mirror life, as well as the need to recognise and protect the benefits of basic research in any potential future governance efforts. Some in-person participants suggested including a principle calling for the development of countermeasures for mirror organisms, as long as these efforts did not themselves advance toward the development of mirror organisms. Others worried that a principle calling for countermeasures development might distract from a primary focus on prevention or appear as tacit acceptance that mirror organisms would be developed. Another participant suggested a principle, inspired from the governance of ozone-depleting substances, that the scientific community should seek alternative paths to attain the benefits of mirror biology without the need to create mirror life. In a cross-track debrief session after the workshop, one participant suggested a principle of haste—that efforts to understand and manage the risks of mirror life should proceed with care but without unnecessary delay.

Finally, participants in both the pre-conference and in-person groups were uncertain about when it might become feasible to create mirror life. Some believed that it might be possible in as little as a decade, while one participant argued that it was a remote scientific possibility.

Engaging stakeholders globally

The afternoon session centered on which stakeholders needed to be involved in the potential governance of mirror organisms and how they should best be involved. As a starting point for discussion, the group considered a list of potential stakeholders adapted from the World Health Organization's Global Guidance Framework for the Responsible Use of the Life Sciences:¹⁶ national governments, scientists and research institutions, private funding bodies including philanthropy, publishers and editors, standard-setting institutions, educators, international organizations, civil society networks and publics, and industry groups.

At both the pre-conference virtual roundtable and the in-person discussion, there was broad agreement that international engagement was essential for managing the risks of mirror life and that input from a broad range of stakeholders other than scientists would be important in making any plans for governance. Both groups also strongly agreed that national governments would be key partners. Many in both groups recommended engaging with international forums such as the WHO and the UN. Several participants recommended connecting with professional associations, especially in developing countries, and intergovernmental organizations in South America and Africa, including the African Union and Africa CDC. Others recommended establishing communication with conservation and environmental organizations, and suggested framing outreach in terms of the One Health

approach to global public health of humans, animals, and ecosystems as an integrated entity. Industry groups would be important to engage in order to address concerns about the potential practical benefits of mirror organisms. Some participants objected to the term “educators,” preferring “communicators and social scientists” to emphasize that two-way dialogue was necessary. The pre-conference group also noted a clear need for the continued involvement of scientists in providing input for governance, evaluating risks and benefits of mirror organisms, detecting mirror life if it were to come to exist, and developing potential countermeasures.

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The group was uncertain about how to effectively engage civil society networks and publics, recognizing the importance of transparency and public engagement while expressing concerns about mis- and disinformation. One participant suggested engaging groups that might otherwise be underrepresented in global public health discussions, such as unions and religious groups. Several participants agreed that public engagement should be pursued with clear questions in mind to learn from the public, scientific materials that equip the public to offer informed opinions, consistent communication, and a stance of open-minded listening.

The group also discussed the role of the national security sector in the governance of mirror organisms. Several participants recommended proactive engagement with national security departments and agencies, arguing that the risks of

mirror organisms should be considered a national security priority. Another participant recommended that it be made clear to national security departments and agencies that mirror organisms would not serve any legitimate military purpose.

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The group considered how to plan timing and coordinate outreach to different stakeholder groups. Several participants stressed the importance of building initial agreement and common terminology among global scientific communities to the extent possible; one participant argued that similar efforts were helpful for coordinating the governance of natural and synthetic embryonic models. Another participant recommended reaching out to scientists and

science institutions, funders of life-science research, and policymakers, in that order. Others suggested proactive efforts to reach the public in order to “pre-bunk” potential misunderstandings.

At the end of the session, the group summarized several potential next steps for stakeholders actively involved in advancing deliberation on mirror life. While the group voiced no disagreement with the potential governance principles under discussion, they recommended refining the language and considering whether to include additional principles on countermeasures and on capturing potential benefits of mirror biology. Many participants also suggested strengthening outreach strategy, including a glossary with crisp definitions of terms, accessible reading materials, and slide decks that communicate the key ideas and the seriousness of the issue. Several also suggested more carefully considering a public engagement strategy and encouraged including additional perspectives in virtual roundtables and other future events.

Policy Interface

Summary

In the Policy Interface workshop track, a group of 19 scientists, policy advisors, and security experts discussed the risks of mirror life and potential policy priorities for addressing them. The goals of the track were to establish a shared understanding of the science of mirror life, to identify promising short-term (<12 month) and long-term policy priorities, and to plan for future discussions.

Participants broadly agreed with the following points:

1. Despite some remaining scientific uncertainties, there is sufficient evidence of the substantial risks and minimal potential benefits of mirror organisms to begin developing and assessing governance measures to ensure that they are not created.
2. Public and private funders should make public statements indicating that they will not fund research with the goal of creating mirror organisms, at least in the near-term, unless future research clearly demonstrates that they would not pose severe risks.
3. Effective governance should be multi-layered and include norms, soft law, and hard law.
4. The input of technical experts will be important for identifying potential regulatory boundaries around precursor technologies for mirror organisms.
5. Global engagement with a wide variety of stakeholders is essential for any policy development efforts.

The severity of risks from mirror life

The morning's discussions began with a short briefing reviewing the main points from the previous day's presentations about the feasibility of

mirror life, its risks and potential benefits, and the feasibility of containment and countermeasures.

The group agreed that based on current evidence, mirror life should not be created because of its potentially catastrophic risks, and that the plausible potential benefits of mirror life were minimal compared to its risks. The primary practical benefit discussed was as a means of producing mirror-image biomolecules on a larger scale, which may have scientific and practical utility. Some participants considered whether chemical synthesis technologies could be improved to a degree that made mirror life unnecessary for even this purpose. However, several participants found it difficult to even imagine a potential benefit that would offset the risks of creating mirror life as they are currently understood.

The group also broadly agreed that despite residual scientific uncertainties, there was sufficient scientific evidence to begin considering options for governance. Several noted that it would become more difficult to take action later on if research and investment continue. Others asked for more clarification about potential timelines and milestones to the creation of mirror life that could be used as points for regulation. Some participants were also interested in the potential for AI to accelerate the development of mirror life.

Potential short-term policy priorities

Several policy options were discussed, including the following:

1. "Relevant stakeholders publicly endorse the view that mirror life should not be created and state that synthetic biology research should be preserved to the extent possible"

2. “Public and private funders make clear that they will not fund research specifically toward the creation of mirror life”
3. “Multilateral organisation declaration against the creation of mirror life and in favor of preserving benefits of mirror-image biomolecule research”
4. “Policymakers engage in and support deliberative processes to establish durable governance to prevent creation of mirror life”

The group agreed that a productive short-term policy goal would be for public and private funders to release statements indicating that they would not fund research with the goal of creating mirror life. Voluntary funding restrictions have direct short-term impact, help to build global norms against mirror life, and can typically be implemented more quickly and easily than legislation. The group discussed some formulations of potential funder statements, such as “Research with the goal of creating mirror cells capable of self-replication should not be pursued and will not be funded,” but did not settle on any final language.

The group also distinguished voluntary restrictions from bans or moratoria. A ban implies an external entity imposing a restriction from the outside, and a moratorium implies a temporary halt to work that is already underway. In contrast, a voluntary restriction of funding would be a self-imposed and indefinite refusal to fund potential future projects that have not yet been proposed.

Several participants emphasized that effective governance would require translating complex scientific concepts into terms that policymakers and the public could understand. Clear communication could reduce the risks that governments implement ineffective regulations or over-regulate and unnecessarily hinder broader progress in synthetic biology. One participant proposed developing more accessible written

materials, such as a one-page policy summary, and establishing a working group on communications. Relatedly, the group repeatedly noted that clear shared definitions of mirror life and related enabling technologies would be helpful for developing policy. For example, several participants suggested moving away from the term “mirror life” toward “mirror bacteria,” “mirror cells,” or “mirror organisms.”

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Potential long-term policy priorities

The group also considered a list of possible long-term policy priorities:

1. “Secure systems for monitoring purchase of mirror life precursor materials”
2. “National security and international coordination infrastructure to prevent creation of mirror life”
3. “Open, transparent, and international research into potential countermeasures”
4. “Laws and regulations on enabling technologies to prevent creation of mirror life”
5. “Existing or new international treaties governing enabling technologies to prevent creation of mirror life”

The group agreed that the development of small mirror-image biomolecules should continue, that the creation of mirror life should be prevented, and that the governance of some enabling technologies for mirror life would likely be necessary. One participant evoked the metaphor of a firebreak to express the idea that prudent governance of

enabling technologies could prevent scientists from advancing to mirror life. However, the group was very uncertain about where or how to draw regulatory lines and which activities or technologies should be permitted, regulated, prohibited, or otherwise governed. Participants agreed that more technical input from synthetic biologists would be critically important.

Several participants also noted that “regulation does not mean a ban” and suggested that access controls and licensing regimes should be considered as tools in some cases. One participant suggested that a top long-term priority should be for national governments and funding agencies to simply turn their short-term refusals to fund research with the goal of creating mirror life into more permanent legislation. Another endorsed the idea of creating a licensing process to monitor and control access to precursor materials for mirror life.

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The group agreed that, while potentially valuable, countermeasures for mirror life should not be a core policy solution because they do not currently appear to be capable of substantially reducing risks. Multiple participants suggested that countermeasures research should be approached with caution to avoid creating false confidence or the perception that recovery is assured. Others argued that any research into countermeasures should be carried out collaboratively and transparently to avoid triggering misperceptions of adversarial intent among nation-states. Some participants suggested that it would be important to engage with national security and defense R&D

agencies to emphasize the risks of attempting to develop mirror life or countermeasures.

The group emphasized that no single governance mechanism would be sufficient and that multiple mechanisms would be needed. Several participants argued that it would likely be best to focus first on international soft-law efforts that establish norms and provide technical recommendations for future national legislation. Some also recommended avoiding prematurely pursuing an international binding treaty, which they argued could be time-consuming, difficult, and likely to make governments feel pressure to conform before they could fully understand the issue.

Instead of attempting to advance or endorse a binding treaty, international organizations such as the WHO, UNESCO, FAO, Interpol, and OECD and intergovernmental networks such as the G7, G20, and ASEAN could reinforce norms, provide technical expertise, and/or implement various forms of soft law to help individual countries implement their own regulations. The group agreed that it would be a powerful signal for international bodies to jointly affirm that mirror life research is profoundly concerning and warrants collective restraint. One participant cited a historical example of an expert group at WHO successfully preventing a high-risk research proposal through a non-binding statement, demonstrating the influence such organizations can exert even without legal authority.

Participants also agreed that it would be critical to expand engagement with stakeholders from across the globe, including developing nations and the Global South. It was argued that global inclusion is morally necessary, because the entire planet could plausibly be affected by mirror life, and that it is tactically necessary for building international coalitions to ensure that no actors unilaterally create mirror life. The upcoming Singapore conference in 2026 was identified as an

opportunity to include a wider range of global stakeholders, though several participants called for earlier engagement.

Potential future work

The group suggested several potential next steps for stakeholders who are interested in advancing conversations on mirror life:

- Stakeholders should draft and share model language for funders to refuse to support research with the goal of creating mirror life.
- A working group of stakeholders should develop a communication strategy for explaining the risks of mirror life while preserving the benefits of synthetic biology to the extent possible (for example, by distinguishing between mirror life and mirror-image biomolecules). This should include a one-page document for policymakers that uses clear and consistent terminology to outline the threat and proposed next steps.
- Stakeholders should expand their engagement with potential partners, including academies of science, international organizations, and representatives from developing countries and the Global South.

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Cross-track discussion

During a cross-track debrief among participants from all five workshop tracks, some members of the Policy Interface track made several additional points not captured in the workshop discussion. One noted that their discussion was framed largely in terms of risk and benefit, but that other ethical frameworks might use other concepts and that it would be important to engage ethicists on issues related to mirror life. Another expressed concern that disagreements about particular enabling technologies might overlook what they saw as the vital importance of ensuring that mirror life was not created. They argued that constraints on multiple technologies could be necessary to ensure this outcome and resisted the temptation to rely on a single “firebreak.”

References

1. NSF Award Search: Award # 1935372 [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 14]. Available from: https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=1935372
2. NSF Award Search: Award # 1935120 [Internet]. [cited 2025 Aug 14]. Available from: https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=1935120
3. Brewster JH, Laskowski M Jr. Left-handed comments. *Science*. 1992 Nov 20;258(5086):1289; author reply 1290.
4. Bohannon J. Mirror-Image Cells Could Transform Science — or Kill Us All. *Wired* [Internet]. 2010 Nov 29 [cited 2025 Aug 20]; Available from: <https://www.wired.com/2010/11/ff-mirrorlife/>
5. Adamala KP, Agashe D, Belkaid Y, Bittencourt DM de C, Cai Y, Chang MW, et al. Confronting risks of mirror life. *Science*. 2024 Dec 20;386(6728):1351–3.
6. Adamala KP, Agashe D, Binder D, Cai Y, Cooper V, Duncombe R, et al. Technical report on mirror bacteria: Feasibility and risks [Internet]. Stanford Digital Repository; 2025 [cited 2025 Aug 15]. Available from: <https://purl.stanford.edu/cv716pj4036>
7. Zimmer C. A “Second Tree of Life” Could Wreak Havoc, Scientists Warn. *The New York Times* [Internet]. 2024 Dec 12 [cited 2025 Aug 14]; Available from: <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/12/12/science/mirror-life-microbes-research.html>
8. Peel M, Cookson C. Synthetic “mirror” microbes pose unprecedented threat to life, scientists warn. *Financial Times* [Internet]. 2024 Dec 12 [cited 2025 Aug 14]; Available from: <https://www.ft.com/content/af39c5f1-3c7c-4097-897b-6793cddf658d>
9. Herzberg N, Larousserie D. [Scientists call for a public debate on research into mirror bacteria, which could “wipe out life on Earth.”] (in French). *Le Monde* [Internet]. 2025 Mar 17 [cited 2025 Aug 14]; Available from: https://www.lemonde.fr/sciences/article/2025/03/17/l-inquietant-spectre-des-bacteries-miroirs_6582641_1650684.html
10. [Liu Yidong: Warning bells ring! How to effectively respond to technology risks under accelerated AI development] (in Mandarin) [Internet]. 2025 [cited 2025 Aug 14]. Available from: <https://china.qianlong.com/2025/0423/8475313.shtml>
11. Cohen J. Fifty years after “Asilomar,” scientists meet again to debate biotech’s modern-day threats. 2025 Mar 5 [cited 2025 Aug 14]; Available from: <https://www.science.org/content/article/fifty-years-after-asilomar-scientists-meet-again-debate-biotech-s-modern-day-threats>
12. Risks from Mirror Life [Internet]. Rice Research Repository, “Spirit of Asilomar and the Future of Biotechnology.” 2025 [cited 2025 Aug 14]. Available from: <https://repository.rice.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/03831782-2fe2-4b00-82ef-781e9c8a0353/content>
13. Paris Conference on Risks from Mirror Life. Symposium on Risks from Mirror Life [Internet]. YouTube; 2025 [cited 2025 Aug 14]. Available from: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLk0HhhNqZqCYDvdAMXStSEBelEb4CS1AY>
14. Berg P, Baltimore D, Brenner S, Roblin RO 3rd, Singer MF. Asilomar conference on recombinant DNA molecules. *Science*. 1975 Jun 6;188(4192):991–4.
15. Berg P. Meetings that changed the world: Asilomar 1975: DNA modification secured. *Nature*. 2008 Sep 18;455(7211):290–1.

16. World Health Organization. Global guidance framework for the responsible use of the life sciences: mitigating biorisks and governing dual-use research [Internet]. World Health Organization; 2022 Sep [cited 2025 Jul 28]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240056107>
17. Gibson DG, Young L, Chuang RY, Venter JC, Hutchison CA 3rd, Smith HO. Enzymatic assembly of DNA molecules up to several hundred kilobases. *Nat Methods*. 2009 May;6(5):343–5.
18. Gibson DG, Glass JI, Lartigue C, Noskov VN, Chuang RY, Algire MA, et al. Creation of a bacterial cell controlled by a chemically synthesized genome. *Science*. 2010 Jul 2;329(5987):52–6.
19. Hutchison CA 3rd, Chuang RY, Noskov VN, Assad-Garcia N, Deerinck TJ, Ellisman MH, et al. Design and synthesis of a minimal bacterial genome. *Science*. 2016 Mar 25;351(6280):aad6253.
20. Xu Y, Zhu TF. Mirror-image T7 transcription of chirally inverted ribosomal and functional RNAs. *Science*. 2022 Oct 28;378(6618):405–12.
21. Kosaka Y, Miyawaki Y, Mori M, Aburaya S, Nishizawa C, Chujo T, et al. Autonomous ribosome biogenesis in vitro. *Nat Commun*. 2025 Jan 8;16(1):514.
22. Clark DP, Cronan JE. Two-carbon compounds and fatty acids as carbon sources. *EcoSal Plus* [Internet]. 2005 Nov;1(2). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1128/ecosalplus.3.4.4>
23. Tong M, French S, El Zahed SS, Ong WK, Karp PD, Brown ED. Gene dispensability in *Escherichia coli* grown in thirty different carbon environments. *MBio* [Internet]. 2020 Sep 29;11(5). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1128/mBio.02259-20>
24. Wishart DS, Guo A, Oler E, Wang F, Anjum A, Peters H, et al. HMDB 5.0: The Human Metabolome Database for 2022. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2022 Jan 7;50(D1):D622–31.
25. Takeuchi O, Hoshino K, Akira S. Cutting edge: TLR2-deficient and MyD88-deficient mice are highly susceptible to *Staphylococcus aureus* infection. *J Immunol*. 2000 Nov 15;165(10):5392–6.
26. Picard C, von Bernuth H, Ghandil P, Chrabieh M, Levy O, Arkwright PD, et al. Clinical features and outcome of patients with IRAK-4 and MyD88 deficiency. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2010 Nov;89(6):403–25.
27. Miller SM, Simon RJ, Ng S, Zuckermann RN, Kerr JM, Moos WH. Comparison of the proteolytic susceptibilities of homologous L-amino acid, D-amino acid, and N-substituted glycine peptide and peptoid oligomers. *Drug Dev Res*. 1995 May;35(1):20–32.
28. Uppalapati M, Lee DJ, Mandal K, Li H, Miranda LP, Lowitz J, et al. A potent d-protein antagonist of VEGF-A is nonimmunogenic, metabolically stable, and longer-circulating in vivo. *ACS Chem Biol*. 2016 Apr 15;11(4):1058–65.
29. Gulec Koksall Z, Bilgic Eltan S, Topyildiz E, Sezer A, Keles S, Celebi Celik F, et al. MHC class II deficiency: Clinical, immunological, and genetic insights in a large multicenter cohort. *J Allergy Clin Immunol Pract*. 2024 Sep;12(9):2490–502.e6.
30. Fan C, Deng Q, Zhu TF. Bioorthogonal information storage in L-DNA with a high-fidelity mirror-image Pfu DNA polymerase. *Nat Biotechnol*. 2021 Dec;39(12):1548–55.
31. Pech A, Achenbach J, Jahnz M, Schülzchen S, Jarosch F, Bordusa F, et al. A thermostable d-polymerase for mirror-image PCR. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2017 Apr 20;45(7):3997–4005.

Glossary

Bacteriophage / Phage: A virus that can infect and replicate inside of a bacterial host.

Booting: A protocol to assemble non-living components (e.g. a genome, transcription-translation machinery, and lipid membrane) into a living synthetic cell.

Bottom-up pathway to mirror life: A proposed strategy for creating a mirror organism by assembling and booting it from individual non-living components (e.g. a genome, transcription-translation system, and membrane). See also “Top-down pathway to mirror life.”

Chirality / chiral: The property of an object not being superimposable onto its mirror image.

Crossover translation system: A hypothetical biological system that would allow a natural-chirality translation system to produce mirror-image proteins using an engineered “crossover ribosome.”

Enantiomers: Mirror-image pairs of chiral objects, such as left and right hands.

Lysate: A solution containing cytoplasmic extract.

Mirror bacteria: Bacteria composed of mirror-image biomolecules; expected to be the simplest (and thus first) viable form of mirror life that could be constructed.

Mirror-image (bio)molecules: Molecules or biomolecules with chiral molecular structures that are mirror images of their naturally-occurring counterparts.

Mirror life / organisms: Hypothetical life forms composed of mirror-image biomolecules.

Protein synthesis Using Recombinant Elements (PURE): A modular reconstituted cell-free translation system composed of purified transcription and translation machinery that enables the synthesis of proteins.

Ribosome: A macromolecular complex composed of ribosomal RNA and ribosomal proteins, found in large numbers within the cytoplasm of cells, that synthesizes proteins based on genetic information from messenger RNA.

Synthetic cell: A hypothetical artificial cell engineered to recreate some or all functions of a biological cell. Synthetic cells can be composed of natural-chirality or mirror-image biomolecules.

Top-down pathway to mirror life: A proposed strategy for creating a mirror organism by converting a living natural-chirality organism into a mirror version in a stepwise process. See also “Bottom-up pathway to mirror life.”

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